

REVEALING THE ORIGIN OF CHEMICAL WEAPONS

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Mirjam de Bruin-Hoegée

Supplementary data for Revealing the Origin of Chemical Weapons

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CHAPTER 2

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary material

Chemical Attribution of Fentanyl: The Effect of Human Metabolism

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- Figure 2. Calibration curves
- Figure 3. Identification of a tentative structure by MS/MS
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PRE-INCUBATION

- 500 μL Buffer: 0.1 M K_3PO_4 , 2.5 mM MgCl_2 (pH = 7.4)
 - 100 μL of 1 mg/mL fentanyl
 - 200 μL of 2.5 mg/mL human liver microsomes
- 3 min., 300 rpm @37 °C

INCUBATION

- 200 μL NADPH-regenerating system:
 - 1 mM NADP^+
 - 5 mM glucose-6-phosphate
 - 1 U/mL glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase
 - 2 mM UDPGA
- 72h, 300 rpm @37 °C

SAMPLE PREPARATION

LC

- Collect 500 μL sample
 - Add 500 μL acetonitrile
- Vortex and centrifuging: 10 min., 14,000 rpm
- Collect supernatant (proteins precipitate)
 - Add 100 μL benzylfentanyl of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
 - Add 400 μL MilliQ
 - Analyse by LC

GC

- Collect 500 μL sample
- Centrifuging: 10 min., 14,000 rpm
- Collect supernatant (proteins precipitate)
 - Add 400 μL DCM and vortex
 - Collect bottom layer
 - Add 100 μL d_5 -norfentanyl of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
 - Analyse by GC

Figure 1. Method for microsomal incubation and sample preparation. LC-Orbitrap-MS © Thermo Fisher Scientific (Bremen). Printed with OTRS permission. GC-MS © Agilent Technologies, Inc. Reproduced with Permission.

Figure 2. Calibration curves of A) Fentanyl with internal standard benzylfentanyl detected by LC-MS/MS. B) Norfentanyl detected by LC-MS/MS. C) Fentanyl detected by GC-MS. D) Norfentanyl with internal standard d_5 -norfentanyl detected by GC-MS.

© Reported with Compound Discoverer 2.1

Figure 3. Typical identification of a tentative structure by LC-Orbitrap-MS/MS reported by Compound Discover 2.1. The impurity identified as N-phenylacetamide (J) is presented. A) Summary of results. B) Chromatogram. C) Mass spectrum. D) MS/MS spectrum.

Figure 4. Effect of leave-one-out validation on PCA robustness. Blue line: PCA including all samples; dashed lines: PCA with one sample left out. For each dashed line another measurement is left out. The PCA model showed good robustness, since leaving out one sample resulted in similar explained variance. A) Pre-metabolism measured by LC-Orbitrap-MS. B) Post-metabolism measured by LC-Orbitrap-MS.

CHAPTER 3

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary data

Post-metabolism impurity profiling of carfentanil, remifentanil, sufentanil, and benzylfentanyl

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1. Method validation LC-MS/MS

Figure S 1. Calibration curves and spiked quality controls of carfentanil, remifentanil, sufentanil, norcarfentanil, benzylfentanyl, and norfentanyl.

Table S 1. Quality control results for carfentanil, remifentanil, sufentanil, norcarfentanil (n=10), and benzylfentanyl (n=9).

Analyte	Level	Concentration (ng/mL)	Accuracy (% of true value)	Precision (RSD%)
Carfentanil	Low	0.5	8	1.5
	Medium	7.5	1.9	1.5
	High	15	3	1.9
Remifentanil	Low	5	11	8
	Medium	50	5	7
	High	100	2.5	2.5
Sufentanil	Low	1	15	2.1
	Medium	10	1.0	1.0
	High	20	1.2	1.6
Norcarfentanil	Low	0.1	2.4	3.4
	Medium	2	2.8	2.7
	High	5	1.7	2.1
Benzylfentanyl	Low	0.5	6	7
	Medium	5	-3	2.3
	High	50	-10	12

2. Impurities remifentaniil

Table S 2. Additional pre- and post-metabolism impurities detected by LC-HRMS/MS for remifentaniil synthesized according to the 7-step and Ugi-method.

Ref.	Name/ biotransformation	Chemical formula	m/z	t _r (min)	Pre, post	Method	Tentative structure
R.E	Hydroxylation of C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO ₃	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO ₃	240.160	7.774	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.F	n.a.	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO	190.123	5.836	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.G	n.a.	C ₁₂ H ₂₇ NO ₂	218.212	6.768	Pre, post	7-step	n.a.
R.H	n.a.	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	219.113	6.039	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.I	n.a.	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO ₂	224.165	11.027	Pre, post	7-step, Ugi	n.a.
R.J	n.a.	C ₁₂ H ₂₇ NO ₃	234.207	7.041	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.K	n.a.	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ NO ₂	244.228	8.739	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.L	n.a.	C ₁₄ H ₃₁ NO ₂	246.243	8.487	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.M	n.a.	C ₁₂ H ₂₇ NO ₄	250.202	21.75	Post	7-step	n.a.
R.N	n.a.	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO ₂	258.149	12.253	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.O	n.a.	C ₁₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	259.202	7.450	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.P	n.a.	C ₁₅ H ₃₃ NO ₂	260.259	9.248	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.Q	n.a.	C ₁₆ H ₃₅ NO ₂	274.275	9.938	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.R	n.a.	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₃	290.176	12.252	Pre, post	Ugi	n.a.
R.S	n.a.	C ₁₆ H ₃₅ NO ₃	290.270	8.618	Pre	7-step	n.a.
R.T	n.a.	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃	292.166	4.655	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.U	n.a.	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂	320.234	9.303	Post	Ugi	n.a.
R.V	n.a.	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O	349.178	5.279	Post	7-step	n.a.

*Identification with Compound Discoverer; †Identification and tentative structure determined by comparison with literature

3. Impurities carfentanil

Table S 3. Additional pre- and post-metabolism impurities detected by LC-HRMS/MS for carfentanil synthesized according to the 7-step and Ugi method.

Ref.	Name/ biotransformation	Chemical formula	m/z	t _r (min)	Synthetic route	Pre, post	Tentative structure
C.H	n.a. [1]	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO	218.154	10.09	Ugi	Pre	n.a.
C.I	n.a. [1]	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ NO ₂	222.149	9.19	Ugi	Pre	n.a.
C.J	n.a.	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂	234.149	18.04	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.K	Hydroxylation of C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂ (C.J) OR dihydroxylation of C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO (C.H)	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₃	250.144	4.98	Ugi	Post	n.a.
C.L	n.a. [1]	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO ₂	258.149	18.05	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.M	n.a. [1]	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ NO ₃	290.176	18.05	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.N	Hydroxylation of C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₃ ‡	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₄	306.171	8.54	Ugi	Post	n.a.
C.O	n.a.	C ₂₀ H ₄₁ NO	312.327	24.88	7-step	Pre, post	n.a.
C.P	n.a. [1]	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	319.202	5.56	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.Q	n.a. [1]	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₃ O	324.208	11.04	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.R	n.a. [1]	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₂	329.202	13.42	Ugi	Pre	n.a.
C.S	n.a. [1]	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	329.223	11.38	Ugi	Post	n.a.
C.T	Hydroxylation of C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ (C.P)	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	335.197	4.79	Ugi	Post	n.a.
C.U	n.a.	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃	335.233	18.04	Ugi	Pre, post	n.a.
C.V	Hydroxylation of C ₁₉ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ (C.U)	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₄	351.228	8.54	Ugi	Post	n.a.
C.W	n.a. [1]	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	367.202	16.87, 11.30	Ugi, 7-step	Pre	n.a.
C.X	n.a.	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ N ₃	374.260	14.64	Ugi	Pre	n.a.
C.Y	Dihydroxylation + glucuronidation of C ₂₀ H ₄₁ NO (C.O) ‡	C ₂₆ H ₄₉ NO ₉	520.349	11.44	7-step	Post	n.a.

*Identification with Compound Discoverer; †Identification and tentative structure determined by comparison with literature; ‡Metabolites from pre-metabolism impurities not included in list because area was below threshold, ^{GC}Compound also detected using GC-MS.

4. Match criterion approach

Table S 4. Characteristic relative responses of remifentanil impurities for the 7-step and Ugi-method. The 95% confidence interval is shown (n=6). Responses are relative to the peak area of remifentanil acid.

Impurity	7-step (%)	Ugi (%)
Aniline	0 - 1.01	16.1 - 17.8
R.T	0 - 0.01	17.3 - 30.6
R.U	0 - 0.082	6.7 - 7.2
R.R	0 - 0.082	1.89 - 3.31
R.H	0 - 0.008	0.54 - 2.91
R.P	0 - 0.0059	0.74 - 2.85
R.S	0 - 0.0052	1.19 - 1.32
R.M	0.17 - 0.34	0.17 - 0.25
R.D	0.012 - 0.037	0.0002 - 0.0077
R.L	0 - 0.19	0.0007 - 0.0009
R.V	0 - 0.007	0.011 - 0.04
R.N	0.003 - 0.007	0.0018 - 0.027

Table S 5. Characteristic relative responses of carfentanil impurities for the 7-step (n=9) and Ugi-method (n=19). The 95% confidence interval is shown. Responses are relative to the peak area of carfentanil.

Impurity	7-step (%)	Ugi (%)
C.AZ	24 - 732	42 - 210
C.AN	1.17 - 3.07	11.8 - 22.3
C.AK	2.69 - 6.54	6.54 - 13.85
C.AX	0.75 - 6.83	18.7 - 67.4
C.AE	0 - 294	0 - 585
C.AL	2.82 - 6.86	4.38 - 12.15
C.AS	34 - 315	0 - 57
C.AV	1.14 - 3.11	3.57 - 54.37
C.AW	0 - 27.5	5.9 - 25.2
C.AY	1.26 - 3.26	2.13 - 6.05
C.AM	1.28 - 3.32	1.67 - 18.03
C.AT	1.37 - 3.54	5.67 - 49.75
C.AU	1.42 - 3.65	5.45 - 39.54

5. Multivariate analysis remifentanil

5.1. PCA

Figure S2. PCA-score plot of pre-metabolism samples of remifentanil synthesized by the 7-step (red circle) and Ugi (blue square) method. B) Corresponding PCA loading plot with highlighted impurities.

Figure S3. Leave-one-out validation of PCA model for remifentanil samples A) pre-metabolism and B) post-metabolism. Blue line includes all samples. Dashed lines represent the variance when one sample is left out.

5.2. LDA

Figure S 4. Tippett plots with cumulative likelihood ratio (LR) distributions for post-metabolism remifentanyl samples. A) Without correction. B) With ELUB bounds. The dashed lines show $LR = 1$.

Figure S 5. LDA score plot of first four principal components of PCA (94% of the variance). B) Corrected distribution of \log_{10} LRs with ELUB bounds, for remifentanyl pre-metabolism samples of 7-step synthesis (red) and Ugi method (blue), analyzed with LC-HRMS/MS. The bars show the frequency of the measurements, and the shaded curves represent the kernel density estimations.

Figure S 6. Tippett plots with cumulative likelihood ratio (LR) distributions for pre-metabolism remifentanyl samples. A) Without correction. B) With ELUB bounds. The dashed lines show $LR = 1$.

6. Multivariate analysis carfentanil

6.1. PCA

Figure S 7. PCA-score plot of pre-metabolism samples of carfentanil synthesized by the 7-step (red circle) and Ugi (blue square) method. B) Corresponding PCA loading plot with highlighted impurities.

Figure S 8. Leave-one-out validation of PCA model for carfentanil samples A) pre-metabolism and B) post-metabolism. Blue line includes all samples. Dashed lines represent the variance when one sample is left out.

6.2. LDA

Figure S 9. Tippet plots with cumulative likelihood ratio (LR) distributions for post-metabolism carfentanil samples. A) Without correction. B) With ELUB bounds. The dashed lines show $LR = 1$.

Figure S 10. LDA score plot of first six principal components of PCA (82% of the variance). B) Corrected distribution of \log_{10} LRs with ELUB bounds, for carfentanil pre-metabolism samples of 7-step synthesis (red) and Ugi method (blue), analyzed with LC-HRMS/MS. The bars show the frequency of the measurements, and the shaded curves represent the kernel density estimations.

Figure S 11. Tippet plots with cumulative likelihood ratio (LR) distributions for pre-metabolism carfentanil samples. A) Without correction. B) With ELUB bounds. The dashed lines show $LR = 1$.

References

- [1] L. Mören, P. Lindén, J. Qvarnström, M. Engqvist, M. Carlsson, R. Afshin Sander, S. Lindberg, A. Larsson, A. Östin, Classification of carfentanil synthesis methods based on chemical impurity profile, *Forensic Chemistry* 26 (2021) 100355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forc.2021.100355>.

CHAPTER 4

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Elucidation of in vitro chlorinated tyrosine adducts in blood plasma as selective biomarkers of chlorine exposure

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- Table S9. Fragmentation pattern of peptide HY(Cl₂)EGSTVPEKK

S1. Method optimization and validation

The LC-MS/MS method was optimized for Cl-Tyr (t_r : 6.15 min) and di-Cl-Tyr (t_r : 6.57 min) with $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -3-chloro-L-tyrosine (t_r : 6.14 min) as internal standard. Linear calibration curves were obtained in the range of 1-100 ng/mL with $R^2 = 0.9992$ - 0.9999 (Figure S1). The mean values for the quality controls were within 20% at 1 ng/mL and within 6% relative standard deviation at both 10 ng/mL and 100 ng/mL ($n = 10$, for each concentration). The stability of the analytes was assessed over two weeks and the concentration was within 15% of the nominal value. The sample preparation efficiency of the pronase digest, determined by spiking known concentrations of analyte into human plasma, were respectively $59\% \pm 9\%$ for Cl-Tyr and $56\% \pm 15\%$ for di-Cl-Tyr. The ionization efficiency was slightly improved by the addition of 0.5% formic acid solution of 10 v% in water.

In addition, the influence of the plasma surface area on the effect of the chlorine exposure was examined. It was found that increasing the surface area with a factor of approximately 10 by using the laboratory glass bottle setup instead of a 15 mL polypropylene Corning tube resulted in a 5-7-fold increase in detected Cl-Tyr level in plasma ($n = 3$). Furthermore, it was found that increasing the exposure time from 2 hours to 48 hours did not significantly increase the degree of chlorination (concentrations were within the error range of ± 1 stdv.). This was expected because blood plasma rapidly consumes chlorine. Finally, prolonging the pronase digestion duration beyond 48 hours did not significantly affect the detected levels of Cl-Tyr and di-Cl-Tyr.

Figure S1. Calibration curves of 3-chlorotyrosine (Cl-Tyr) and 3,5-dichlorotyrosine (di-Cl-Tyr) with internal standard $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -3-chloro-L-tyrosine, detected by LC-MS/MS.

Figure S2. Heatmap of peptides identified with LC-HRMS/MS after pepsin digestion of human blood plasma, with corresponding average percentage of chlorinated tyrosines for non-exposed, low, medium, and high chlorine exposure.

Table S1. Extent of protein chlorination for various chlorine exposure levels after digestion by pepsin (n = 3, \pm SD).

Chlorine exposure level	Average percentage of chlorinated tyrosines (%)
Blank	1.2 \pm 0.4
Low	0.7 \pm 0.6
Medium	3.2 \pm 1.5
High	14 \pm 9

Table S2. Extent of overall protein chlorination for various chlorine exposure levels after digestion by trypsin (n = 3, \pm SD).

Chlorine exposure level	Average percentage of chlorinated tyrosines (%)
Blank	0.2 \pm 0.3
Low	0.5 \pm 0.5
Medium	2.3 \pm 1.8
High	16.2 \pm 2.1

Table S3. Identified biomarkers for chlorine exposure after trypsin and pepsin digestion.

Long peptide	Enzyme	Accession	Protein	Mass	t _R (min)	Cl (#) ^a	N (#) ^b
AHY(CI)GGFTVQNEANK	Trypsin	P02675 FIBB_HUMAN	Fibrinogen beta chain	1568.7	18.5	1	2
AIGY(CI)LNTGYQR	Trypsin	P01023 A2MG_HUMAN	Alpha-2- macroglobulin	1288.6	20.2	1	1
ALSHAVNNY(CI)HK	Trypsin	P04114 APOB_HUMAN	Apolipoprotein B-100	1286.6	15.3	1	2
ASAGLLGAHAAAITAY(CI)	Trypsin	P0COL4 CO4A_HUMAN	Complement C4- A	1490.7	21.6	1	1
ATVLNY(CI)LPK	Trypsin	P01023 A2MG_HUMAN	Alpha-2- macroglobulin	1051.5	21.9	1	3 ^c
AVRPGY(CI)PK	Trypsin	n.a.	n.a.	920.5	15.9	1	4 ^c
DDLY(CI)VSDAFHK	Trypsin	P01008 ANT3_HUMAN	Antithrombin-III	1342.6	20.4	1	3
FSVY(CI)AK	Trypsin	P02765 FETUA_HUMAN	Alpha-2-HS- glycoprotein	846.4	20.3	1	3
GEVPPRY(CI)PR	Trypsin	P02790 HEMO_HUMAN	Hemopexin	1103.5	16.6	1	1
GGTSY(CI)GTGSETESPR	Trypsin	P02671 FIBA_HUMAN	Fibrinogen alpha chain	1605.6	16.3	1	2
GLSVY(CI)ADKPETTK	Trypsin	P02763 A1AG1_HUMAN	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1	1441.7	18.2	1	1
GVALHRPDVY(CI).LLPPAR	Trypsin	P01871 IGHM_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin heavy constant mu	1159.6	19.1	1	2
GY(CI)TQQLAFR	Trypsin	P01024 CO3_HUMAN	Complement C3	1116.5	20.5	1	2
AP.HGPGLIY(CI)R	Trypsin	P02765 FETUA_HUMAN	Alpha-2-HS- glycoprotein	1113.5	19.2	1	1
HNHY(CI)TQKSLSLSPG	Pepsin	P0DOX5 IGG1_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin gamma-1 heavy chain	1601.7	17.4	1	2
R.HPDY(CI)SVVL.LLR	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1500.8	21.5	1	1
HQLY(CI)IDETVNSNIPTNLR	Trypsin	P02675 FIBB_HUMAN	Fibrinogen beta chain	1307.6	14.9	1	2
HY(CI)EGSTVPEK.K	Trypsin	P00738 HPT_HUMAN	Haptoglobin	1307.6	14.9	1	5
HY(CI2)EGSTVPEK.K	Trypsin	P00738 HPT_HUMAN	Haptoglobin	1341.6	15.1	2	3
YE.IARRHPY(CI)F.Y(CI)APEL	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1360.6	20.8	2	1
L.IQPDSVVKPY(CI)R	Trypsin	P02675 FIBB_HUMAN	Fibrinogen beta chain	1435.7	18.6	1	2

IY(CI)GNQDTSSQLK	Trypsin	P19823 ITIH2_HUMAN	Inter-alpha- trypsin inhibitor heavy chain H2	1386.6	17.9	1	1
FA.KRY(CI2)KAAF	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1168.5	19.5	1	2 ^c
FFA.KRY(CI)KAAF	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1281.6	20.6	1	4 ^c
LEDVKKLY(CI)HSEA	Pepsin	P01009 A1AT_HUMAN	Alpha-1- antitrypsin	1464.7	18.3	1	2
KQL.INDY(CI)V.EK	Trypsin	P01011 AACT_HUMAN	Alpha-1- antichymotrypsin	1041.5	18.7	1	3 ^c
LGEVNTY(CI)AGDLQK	Trypsin	P06727 APOA4_HUMAN	Apolipoprotein A-IV	1440.7	20.0	1	2
LLIY(CI)GASTR	Trypsin	n.a.	n.a.	1026.5	21.0	1	1
NSLFEY(CI)QK	Trypsin	P02671 FIBA_HUMAN	Fibrinogen alpha chain	1061.5	20.6	1	3
EEAPSLR.PAPPPISGGGY(CI)R	Trypsin	P02675 FIBB_HUMAN	Fibrinogen beta chain	1984.0	19.6	1	3
SY(CI)STTAVVTNPK	Trypsin	P02766 TTHY_HUMAN	Transthyretin	1300.6	18.1	1	2
TAQEGDHGSHVY(CI).TK	Trypsin	P01023 A2MG_HUMAN	Alpha-2- macroglobulin	1562.7	14.8	1	3
TY(CI)ETTLEK	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1017.4	18.2	1	6
SALE.VDETY(CI)VPK	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1383.6	20.6	1	1
EVDE.TY(CI)VPKE.F	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1388.6	21.7	1	1
VGPEADKY(CI)R	Trypsin	P02679 FIBG_HUMAN	Fibrinogen gamma chain	1067.5	16.3	1	1
IV.VRY(CI)TKKVPQVST.PTL	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1438.8	16.3	1	7 ^c
IV.VRY(CI2)TKKVPQVST.PTL	Pepsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1897.0	20.5	1	4 ^c
WY(CI)VDGVEVH.NAK	Trypsin	P01857 IGHG1_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 1	1449.6	16.0	1	4 ^c
Y(CI)AATSQVLLPSK	Trypsin	P01871 IGHM_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin heavy constant mu	1310.7	20.2	1	2
F.Y(CI)APELFFAK	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1378.7	22.2	1	2
Y(CI)EKPGSPRR	Trypsin	P02751 FINC_HUMAN	Fibronectin	1063.5	15.3	1	1
Y(CI)GAATFTR	Trypsin	P01023 A2MG_HUMAN	Alpha-2- macroglobulin	919.4	18.8	1	2
SI.Y(CI)KPGQTVK	Trypsin	P01023 A2MG_HUMAN	Alpha-2- macroglobulin	1153.6	17.4	1	4

YLQEIY(CI)NSNNQK	Trypsin	P02679 FIBG_HUMAN	Fibrinogen gamma chain	1546.7	19.6	1	1
K.Y(CI)LY(CI)EIAR	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	994.4	21.6	2	3
KK.Y(CI)LYEIAR	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	960.4	20.8	1	4
Y(CI)LY(CI2)EIAR	Trypsin	P02768 ALBU_HUMAN	Albumin	1028.4	21.9	3	1
Y(CI)QQHPGKAPK	Trypsin	P01704 LV214_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin lambda variable 2-14	1186.6	14.3	1	1
Y(CI2)QQKPGKAPK	Trypsin	A0A0C4DH67 KV108_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin kappa variable 1- 8	1594.8	15.2	2	1
Y(CI)QQKPGQAPR	Trypsin	P01619 KV320_HUMAN	Immunoglobulin kappa variable 3- 20	1205.6	14.8	1	5
Y(CI)QTKVDKDLQSL	Pepsin	P02679 FIBG_HUMAN	Fibrinogen gamma chain	1470.7	20.0	1	1
Y(CI)TFELSR	Trypsin	P02774 VTDB_HUMAN	Vitamin D- binding protein	948.4	20.9	1	2
Y(CI)VEKGTQGKIVDL	Pepsin	P01009 A1AT_HUMAN	Alpha-1- antitrypsin	1482.7	20.0	1	1
Y(CI)VGGQEHAH	Trypsin	P02763 A1AG1_HUMAN	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1	1177.5	16.8	1	1

^aNumber of attached chlorine atoms (Cl)

^bPeptides detected in given number of repetitions (N)

^cNot detected in all high chlorine exposure samples

A)

B)

Figure S3. Protein coverage, with sequences identified after pepsin digestion (blue) and trypsin digestion (red). A) Human serum albumin (56% coverage), B) Haptoglobin (33% coverage).

Figure S4. Extracted ion chromatograms of plasma exposed to various chlorine exposure concentrations analyzed by LC-HRMS/MS (Acclaim PepMap C18 column, mobile phase: H₂O (A) and ACN (B) with 0.1% FA), with YLYEIAR at m/z 464.25 and t_R = 20.1-20.7 min (blue), Y(Cl)LYEIAR and YLY(Cl)EIAR at m/z 481.23 and t_R = 20.8-21.0 and 21.0-21.2 min (red), K.Y(Cl)LY(Cl)EIAR at m/z 562.26 and t_R = 20.6-20.8 min (orange), and Y(Cl)LY(Cl)₂EIAR and Y(Cl₂)LY(Cl)EIAR at m/z 515.19 and t_R = 21.7-21.9 and 21.9-22.0 min (green). A) Blank, B) Low exposure, C) Medium exposure, D) High exposure.

S2. Isotope ratios

In the full scan MS spectrum of this doubly charged peptide, a distinct chlorine pattern is visible for single, double and triple chlorination (Figure 6B-D). The unchlorinated peptide showed a single peak as expected (Figure 6A). Because the ^{35}Cl isotope has a natural occurrence of 76% and the ^{37}Cl isotope of 24%, the isotope ratio for the chlorinated peptide can be calculated. When the influence of other isotopes, such as carbon, is also considered, the isotope ratio of a mono-, di- and tri-chlorinated peptide is 2:1 (Figure 6B), 5:4:1 (Figure 6C) and 11:12:5:1 (Figure 6D), respectively.⁴⁹ In Figure 6C, this last peak for the tri-chlorinated peptide was expected at a m/z 518.19, but it was not visible presumably due to its low intensity.

Table S4. Theoretical compared to measured isotope values in full scan MS spectrum analyzed by LC-HRMS/MS of doubly charged chlorinated precursor Y*LY*EIAR.

Chlorination	Theoretical isotope value	Measured isotope value
0	1	1
1	2:1	2:1
2	5:4:1	5:4:1
3	11:12:5:1	11:13:4:0

Table S5. Fragmentation pattern of peptide Y(Cl)LYEIAR with y and b fragments.

#	b (m/z)	Peptide	Y (m/z)	#
1	198.03	Y(+33.96)		7
2	311.12	L	764.43	6
3	474.18	Y	651.35	5
4	603.22	E	488.28	4
5	716.31	I	359.24	3
6	787.34	A	246.16	2
7		R	175.12	1

Figure S5. MS/MS spectrum of parent ion K.Y(Cl)LY(Cl)EIAR with m/z 562.262 at an $t_R = 20.64$ min., detected in the trypsin digest of a plasma sample exposed to 70 and 350 mmol/L chlorine gas. The m/z of the γ -fragments and corresponding amino acids are shown.

Table S6. Fragmentation pattern of peptide Y(Cl)LY(Cl)EIAR with y and b fragments.

#	b (m/z)	Peptide	Y (m/z)	#
1	129.10	K		8
2	326.13	Y(+33.96)	995.41	7
3	439.21	L	798.39	6
4	636.24	Y(+33.96)	685.31	5
5	765.28	E	488.28	4
6	878.36	I	359.24	3
7	949.40	A	246.16	2
8		R	175.12	1

Figure S6. MS/MS spectrum of parent ion Y(Cl)LY(Cl₂)EIAR with m/z 515.194 at an t_R = 21.91 min., detected in the trypsin digest of a plasma sample exposed to 350 mmol/L chlorine gas. The m/z of the y-fragments and corresponding amino acids are shown.

Table S7. Fragmentation pattern of peptide Y(Cl)LY(Cl₂)EIAR with y and b fragments.

#	b (m/z)	Peptide	Y (m/z)	#
1	198.03	Y(+33.96)	1029.4	7
2	311.12	L	832.36	6
3	542.10	Y(+67.92)	719.27	5
4	671.14	E	488.28	4
5	784.23	I	359.24	3
6	855.27	A	246.16	2
7		R	175.12	1

Figure S7. Extracted ion chromatograms of plasma exposed to various chlorine exposure concentrations analyzed by LC-HRMS/MS (Acclaim PepMap C18 column, mobile phase: H₂O (A) and ACN (B) with 0.1% FA), with HEGSTVPEKK at m/z 637.823 and $t_R = 14.3$ -15.0 min (blue), HY(Cl)EGSTVPEKK at m/z 654.805 and $t_R = 14.9$ -15.0 min (orange), and HY(Cl₂)EGSTVPEKK at m/z 671.785 and $t_R = 15.2$ -15.3 min (green). A) Blank, B) Low exposure, C) Medium exposure, D) High exposure.

Table S8. Fragmentation pattern of peptide HY(Cl)EGSTVPEKK with y and b fragments.

#	b	Peptide	y	#
1	138.07	H	1308.60	11
2	335.09	Y(+33.96)	1171.54	10
3	464.14	E	974.52	9
4	521.15	G	845.48	8
5	608.19	S	788.45	7
6	709.24	T	701.42	6
7	808.30	V	600.37	5
8	905.36	P	501.30	4
9	1034.40	E	404.25	3
10	1162.48	K	275.21	2
11		K	147.11	1

Figure S8. MS/MS spectrum of parent ion HY(Cl₂)EGSTVPEKK with m/z 672.648 at an t_R = 15.21 min., detected in the trypsin digest of a plasma sample exposed to 350 mmol/L chlorine gas. The m/z of the y-fragments and corresponding amino acids are shown.

Table S9. Fragmentation pattern of peptide HY(Cl₂)EGSTVPEKK with y and b fragments.

#	b	Peptide	y	#
1	138.07	H	1342.6	11
2	369.05	Y(+67.92)	1205.5	10
3	498.09	E	974.52	9
4	555.12	G	845.47	8
5	642.15	S	788.45	7
6	743.20	T	701.42	6
7	842.26	V	600.37	5
8	939.32	P	501.30	4
9	1068.4	E	404.25	3
10	1196.5	K	275.21	2
11		K	147.11	1

CHAPTER 5

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

On-site detection and laboratory verification of the presence of nerve agent biomarkers using dried blood spots

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1. Biotransformation pathways

Figure S 1. Biotransformation pathways in humans after poisoning with sarin. Two main processes are hydrolysis, and the formation of protein adducts. Albumin, BChE and other protein adducts are then digested or reactivated by fluoride before the analysis.

Figure S 2. To be investigated biotransformation pathways in humans after poisoning with Novichok nerve agents, based on sarin research. Two main processes are hydrolysis, and the formation of protein adducts. Albumin, BChE and other protein adducts are then digested or reactivated by fluoride before the analysis.

2. LC-MS/MS method optimization

Table S 1. Gradient elution settings for LC-MS/MS analyses. Eluent A is water with 0.2% v/v formic acid and eluent B is ACN with 0.2% v/v formic acid.

Analyte	Eluent A (%)	Linear ramping (min)	Eluent A (%)	Linear ramping (min)	Eluent A (%)
FGESAGAAS MPA-FGES(mpa)AGAAS GB-FGES(GB)AGAAS A-230-FGES(A-230)AGAAS A-232-FGES(A-232)AGAAS A-234-FGES(A-234)AGAAS	100	20	20	0.1	100 (hold 5 min)
MPA-Tyr GB-Tyr A-230-Tyr A-232-Tyr A-234-Tyr	100 (hold 1 min)	10	50 (hold 2 min)	0.1	100 (hold 3 min)
MPA IMPA GB Methyl phosphate Ethyl phosphate	100	5	20 (hold 1 min)	0.1	100 (hold 3 min)

Table S 2. Mass spectrometric parameters for nerve agent adducts and metabolites analyzed by LC-MS/MS

Analyte	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)	Cone voltage (V)	Collision energy (eV)
FGESAGAAS	796.4	492.2	60	32
		620.3	60	32
		691.4	60	32
FGES(mpa)AGAAS	874.3	602.3	60	31
		673.3	60	27
		778.3	60	26
FGES(GB)AGAAS	916.3	602.3	60	31
		673.3	60	27
		778.3	60	26
FGES(A-230)AGAAS	970.4	602.3	60	31
		673.3	60	27
		778.3	60	26
FGES(A-232)AGAAS	986.4	602.3	60	31
		673.3	60	27
		778.3	60	26
FGES(A-234)AGAAS	1000.4	602.3	60	31
		673.3	60	27
		778.3	60	26
MPA-Tyr	260.1	197.1	40	13
		214.1	40	13
GB-Tyr	302.1	214.1	40	13
		260.1	40	13
A-234-Tyr	386.2	74.1	40	15
		244.1	40	15
		285.0	40	15
		313.0	40	15
MPA	97.0	65.0	20	26
		79.0	20	26
IMPA	139.0	79.0	20	7
		97.0	20	7
GB	141.0	99.0	20	7
A-230	195.0	73.8	20	9
		121.6	20	10
		177.0	20	15
A-232	211.0	56.2	20	15
		73.8	20	10
		138.1	20	11
A-234	255.1	74.2	20	12
		123.9	20	13
		197.0	20	11

3. GC-MS/MS method optimization and validation

Table S 3. Mass spectrometric parameters for nerve agents analyzed by GC-MS/MS

Analyte	Retention time (min.)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)	Collision energy (V)
GB	7.70	125	99	10
		99	81	15
		99	47	30
A-230	19.19	194	72	5
		165	68	10
		122	81	10
A-232	20.00	210	181	10
		181	68	15
		138	97	15
A-234	20.65	224	195	5
		224	72	5
		195	68	10

Three different blood samples with a relatively low sarin inhibition of 20% were prepared for fluoride reactivation (n=3-5). Also, sarin standards, solvent blanks and blank samples without the addition of KF were added. OPCW criteria for signal-to-noise (S/N) and ion ratio were evaluated. The S/N should be larger than 5 and the ion ratio for a ratio of >50% should be maximum $\pm 20\%$. The standard has an ion-ratio, for 125 \rightarrow 99 with respect to 99 \rightarrow 81, of 83%. The variation must not be larger than $\pm 20\% * 83.2 = \pm 16.6\%$. The obtained ion-ratios and the S/N as shown in Table S4 were according to the guidelines.

Table S 4. Evaluation of ion-ratios and signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios of blood incubated with 20% sarin after fluorite reactivation.

	99 → 81		125 → 99		Ion-ratio (%)	Deviation (%)
	Area	S/N	Area	S/N		
Solventblank1	0		0			
Standard_GB_0.5ng/mL	20964	612	17447	743	83	
Solventblank2	0		0			
Blood1_noKF	0		0			
Blood1_KF_1	26396	392	21500	1028	81	-2
Blood1_KF_2	22880	928	16395	251	72	-14
Blood1_KF_3	27267	1150	23724	202	87	5
Blood1_KF_4	31794	1617	26594	1735	84	1
Blood1_KF_5	31528	1201	25106	1682	80	-4
Solventblank3	0		0			
Blood2_noKF	0		0			
Blood2_KF_1	29042	7187	22301	341	77	-8
Blood2_KF_2	33697	522	26626	760	79	-5
Blood2_KF_3	31312	411	24139	304	77	-7
Solventblank4	0		0			
Blood3_noKF	0		0			
Blood3_KF_1	26677	534	18892	350	71	-15
Blood3_KF_2	30705	241	21918	298	71	-14
Blood3_KF_3	23437	190	18197	3067	78	-7
Solventblank5	0		0			

Figure S 3. Calibration curve of 1-100 ng/mL sarin analyzed by GC-MS/MS ($n=1$, m/z 99 → 81).

4. Cholinesterase activity

Figure S 4. Cholinesterase activity of 10 μ L liquid blood (\square) and 12.5 μ L-based DBS (\circ) extracted after one month following nerve agent incubation. The ratio between blood incubated with 1.3 μ M Novichok nerve agent and non-exposed blood is shown. A) AChE activity after Novichok inhibition ($n=3$), B) BChE activity after Novichok inhibition ($n=3$). Line is of indicative nature only, error bars represent ± 1 standard deviation.

Figure S 5. BChE activity of DBS inhibited with sarin and extracted after one day ($n=3$, positive error bars), one month ($n=8$, negative error bars) and three months ($n=1$) of storage at room temperature.

5. Analysis of free and regenerated nerve agent in liquid blood

Figure S 6. Extracted ion chromatograms of regenerated sarin in 400 μL liquid whole blood exposed to sarin, after fluoride reactivation analyzed by GC-MS/MS (m/z 99 \rightarrow 81, with corresponding area of the peak). A) Reference standard of sarin, B) Blood exposed to sarin without KF addition (control), C) Blood exposed to sarin with KF addition.

Figure S 7. Extracted ion chromatograms of intact Novichok A-232 in 400 μL liquid whole blood exposed to A-232, after fluoride reactivation analyzed by GC-MS/MS (m/z 138 \rightarrow 97). A) Reference standard A-232, B) Dried blood spots exposed to A-232 without KF addition (control), C) DBS exposed to A-232 with KF addition.

Figure S 8. Extracted ion chromatograms of intact Novichok A-234 in 400 μL liquid whole blood exposed to A-234, after fluoride reactivation analyzed by GC-MS/MS (m/z 224 \rightarrow 195). A) Reference standard A-234, B) Dried blood spots exposed to A-234 without KF addition (control), C) DBS exposed to A-234 with KF addition.

6. Analysis of free nerve agent in dried blood spots

Figure S 9. Extracted ion chromatograms of intact Novichok A-C) A-230 (195.0 \rightarrow 73.8) and D-F) A-234 (255.1 \rightarrow 74.2) in dried blood spots (50 μL) analyzed by LC-MS/MS, three days after storage of the dried spots at ambient conditions. A, D) Reference standard, B, E) Dried blood spots exposed to nerve agent without KF addition (control), C, F) DBS exposed to nerve agent with KF addition.

7. Analysis of hydrolysis metabolites in DBS

Figure S 10. Extracted ion chromatograms (139 \rightarrow 97) of 100% inhibited dried blood spots after sarin exposure. A) sample preparation blank, B) potential presence of IMPA in dried blood spots, C) standard of IMPA.

CHAPTER 6

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supporting Information

Verification of exposure to chemical warfare agents through analysis of persistent biomarkers in plants

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- Section A.3. Chromatograms after three months
 - Figure A.5. Extracted ion chromatograms of phosphorylated tyrosine adduct
 - Figure A.6. Extracted ion chromatograms of chlorinated tyrosine adducts
 - Figure A.7. Extracted ion chromatograms of N1-HETE-His and N3-HETE-His adducts
- Table A.1. Identified biomarkers in plants after chlorine, sarin or sulfur mustard exposure

A.1. Method optimization and validation

The gradient elution was optimized for each analyte (Table A.1). The chemicals could be analyzed with a single chromatographic method as well, which is the same as described for the A-234 and GB adducts.

Table A. 1. Gradient elution settings for LC-MS/MS analyses. Eluent A is water with 0.2% v/v formic acid and eluent B is ACN with 0.2% v/v formic acid.

Analyte	Eluent A (%)	Linear ramping (min)	Eluent A (%)	Eluent A (%)
A-234-Tyr GB-Tyr MPA-Tyr	100 (hold 1 min)	10	50 (hold 2 min)	100 (hold 3 min)
Cl-Tyr di-Cl-Tyr ¹³ C ₆ -Cl-Tyr	100 (hold 2 min)	8	20 (hold 2 min)	100 (hold 3 min)
N1-HETE-His N3-HETE-His	100 (hold 3 min)	3	20 (hold 1 min)	100 (hold 3 min)

For GB-Tyr, linear calibration curves were obtained in the range of 0.05 – 20 ng/mL with $R^2 = 0.9997 - 0.99999$ (Figure A.1A). The mean values for the quality controls were within 2.6% relative standard deviation at 0.1, 1 and 10 ng/mL (n=10 for each concentration). The stability of the analyte was assessed over two weeks and the concentration was within 15% of the nominal value for 0.1 ng/mL and within 3.3% for 1 and 10 ng/mL.

In addition, linear calibration curves were obtained in the range of 1 – 100 ng/mL with $R^2 = 0.9999 - 0.99995$ for Cl-Tyr and di-Cl-Tyr as well (Figure A.1B). The mean values for the quality controls were within 20% at 1 ng/mL and within 6% relative standard deviation at both 10 ng/mL and 100 ng/mL (n = 10, for each concentration). The stability of the analytes was assessed over two weeks and the concentration was within 18% of the nominal value for 1 ng/mL and within 3.8% for 10 and 100 ng/mL.

Third, the LC-MS/MS method was validated for N1-HETE-HIS and N3-HETE-HIS. Linear calibration curves were obtained in the range of 1 – 50 ng/mL with $R^2 = 0.9987 - 0.9997$ (Figure A.1C). The mean values of the quality controls were within 5% for 1 and 10 ng/mL N1-HETE-HIS and N3-HETE-HIS (n = 10, for each concentration). The stability of the analytes was assessed over one week and the concentration was within 23% for 1 ng/mL N3-HETE-HIS and within 6% for 1 ng/mL N1-HETE-HIS and 10 ng/mL N1-HETE-HIS and N3-HETE-HIS.

Figure A. 1. Calibration curves analyzed by LC-MS/MS of A) GB-Tyr, B) 3-chlorotyrosine (Cl-Tyr) and 3,5-dichlorotyrosine (di-Cl-Tyr) with internal standard 13C6-3-chloro-L-tyrosine, C) N1-HETE-HIS and N3-HETE-HIS adducts of sulfur mustard.

A.2. Visual examination of vegetation

Figure A. 2. Physical state of nettle leaf upon liquid exposure to A-234.

Figure A. 3. No notable differences were observed for A) Laurel, B) Basil and C) Nettle prior to exposure compared to D) Laurel, E) Basil and F) Nettle immediately after vapor exposure of 25 mg/m³ sarin in the vapor generation set-up.

Figure A. 4. Nettle A) prior to exposure B) after 250 mg/m³ exposure to sarin. It should be noted that the change could also be due to the dry atmosphere in the vapor generation set-up instead as a result of the chemical warfare agent exposure.

A.3. Chromatograms after three months

Figure A. 5. Extracted ion chromatograms of phosphylated tyrosine adduct with $t_R = 8.14$ three months after sarin vapor exposure. A) Sample preparation blank. B) Standard GB-Tyr. C) GB-Tyr measured after plant exposure to 250 mg/m^3 sarin.

Figure A. 6. Extracted ion chromatograms of chlorinated tyrosine adducts three months after chlorine gas exposure. A) Sample preparation blank. B) Standard Cl-Tyr with $t_R = 6.17$ min and di-Cl-Tyr with $t_R = 6.59$ min. C) Cl-Tyr and di-Cl-Tyr after 5 g/m^3 plant exposure.

Figure A. 7. Extracted ion chromatograms of N1-HETE-His and N3-HETE-His adducts three months after sulfur mustard vapor exposure. A) Sample preparation blank. B) Standard N1-HETE-His with $t_R = 4.00$ min and N3-HETE-His with $t_R = 4.26$ min. C) N1-HETE-His and N3-HETE-His measured after 150 mg/m^3 plant exposure.

Table A. 2. Identified biomarkers in plants after chlorine, sarin or sulfur mustard exposure.

Peptide	Accession	Protein	Mass (Da)	t _R (min)	Exposure	Species	N (#) ^a
Y(+120.03)FRLSSLEKCY(+120.03)SR	P93211 14336_SOLLC	14-3-3 protein	1890.9	16.4	GB	Basil	1
KSCSY(+33.96)ELETELSK	P29307 1433_OENEH	14-3-3 protein	1549.7	16.0	Cl	Nettle	1
H(+105.04)DKHELQEAHMK	P93784 14335_SOLTU	14-3-3 protein	1660.8	20.1	HD	Laurel	1
AEEAAEKY(+120.03)RKPAAAEATAAPPR	P49608 ACOC_CUCMA	Aconitate hydratase, cytoplasmic	2417.2	16.1	GB	Basil	1
CY(+120.03)KLLLPPTLVVADKFAFAEHK	O65396 GCST_ARATH	Aminomethyltransferase, mitochondrial	2626.4	21.2	GB	Laurel	1
GYPGY(+33.96)LYTDLATIYER	B0K8E7 VATB_THEP3	ATP synthase	1927.9	21.3	Cl	Nettle	2
MY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)EAKETLELAEAVKR	Q0ZJ14 ATPE_VITVI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2283.1	21.6	GB	Laurel	1
QMLPLCH(+105.04)CQTLLEAEAGGLR	Q2MI94 ATPE_SOLLC	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2287.1	21.6	HD	Basil	1
EAQAVADDVFSLFISEEVDKVELLY(+33.96)TK	Q01908 ATPG1_ARATH	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	3091.5	22.8	Cl	Nettle	2
WEHY(+120.03)FMESLASELAAR	P29790 ATPG_TOBAC	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2058.9	20.2	GB	Laurel	1
KVEY(+120.03)MRVLMGDGLFLQEGSWK	A6MM21 ATPA_BUXMI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2605.3	22.0	GB	Basil	1
NY(+120.03)MQVDPFQESGVLNEENLAESK	Q68RZ9 ATPB_PANGI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2760.2	18.8	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)FKLATSGSGVSTLEK	Q68RZ9 ATPB_PANGI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	1806.9	17.1	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)VGPVADPLDSTPNAVMPR	Q68RZ9 ATPB_PANGI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2118.0	20.8	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)PAVDPLDSFHVVMMPR	Q85V35 ATPB_LACPU	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2118.0	20.7	GB	Basil	1
VGLTALTIAEY(+33.96)FR	O03081 ATPB_PSINU	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	1486.8	21.2	Cl	Nettle	2
VGLTALTIAEY(+67.92)FR	O03081 ATPB_PSINU	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	1520.7	21.6	Cl	Nettle	1
QVY(+120.03)HLNEQNLAESK	Q2L917 ATPB_GOSHI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	1791.9	16.6	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)NMCY(+120.03)RWWRLNEKNLAESK	Q2L917 ATPB_GOSHI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2743.3	19.9	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)Y(+120.03)Y(+120.03)VVLSTEMGTLKER	Q2L917 ATPB_GOSHI	ATP synthase, chloroplasmic	2311.1	20.1	GB	Laurel	1
KYY(+120.03)NMY(+120.03)SPAGYLENK	P19023 ATPB_M_MAIZE	ATP synthase, mitochondrial	2079.9	19.8	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)DADSGGVVLYVK	Q41396 VATE_SPIOL	ATPase	1504.7	18.5	GB	Basil	1
AY(+120.03)ENGLTSVAGR	O80860 FTSH2_ARATH	ATP-dependent zinc metalloprotease, chloroplasmic	1356.6	23.1	GB	Basil	1
EALGKAEKALASLEH(+105.04)KEETLK	Q655S1 FTSH2_ORYSJ	ATP-dependent zinc metalloprotease, chloroplasmic	2641.4	20.3	HD	Basil	1
Y(+33.96)AGVGAAIEYAVLHLK	P42737 BCA2_ARATH	Carbonic anhydrase, chloroplasmic	1707.9	20.9	Cl	Nettle	2
WY(+120.03)WY(+120.03)KLLSSVDLLEEKLR	B9N843 ACCC2_POPTR	Biotin carboxylase, chloroplasmic	2580.3	21.0	GB	Basil	1
H(+105.04)NLTDDQLSEFK	Q39752 CALM_FAGSY	Calmodulin	1550.7	21.4	HD	Laurel	2
GPILLEDY(+33.96)HLVEK	P48350 CATA1_CUCPE	Catalase	1558.8	20.7	Cl	Nettle	1

LPACCAY(+120.03)RLEKENNK	P48350 CATA 1_CUCPE	Catalase	1984.0	16.0	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)FELEQENNKVASSTGK	P48350 CATA 1_CUCPE	Catalase	2177.0	15.9	GB	Basil	1
GPLENLADHLADPVNNNAWAY(+33.96)ATKL CPGK	P09755 CB22 _SOYBN	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	3125.5	22.3	CI	Nettle	2
CY(+120.03)GDYLGPNLLVVPK	P09756 CB23 _SOYBN	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1883.9	20.5	GB	Laurel	1
GY(+120.03)CDYLGPNPSLVVPAR	P09756 CB23 _SOYBN	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1842.9	20.2	GB	Laurel	1
LVY(+120.03)FYLAPELLGK	P27522 CB13 _SOLLC	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1644.9	21.6	GB	Basil	1
DHVKPVSSGSY(+120.03)YGDPR	P04783 CB25 _PETSP	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1882.9	19.0	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)Y(+120.03)PNATGDKGYPGGK	P36494 CB4_ SPIOL	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1826.8	17.8	GB	Basil	1
KLY(+120.03)RYLKFDLDSLQNLAK	Q07473 CB4A _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	2462.3	22.3	GB	Basil	1
NY(+120.03)WELLHGR	Q07473 CB4A _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1306.6	17.8	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)CMVQSTPFQDHRSQLVLR	Q07473 CB4A _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	2526.2	21.8	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)GELLHGR	Q07473 CB4A _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1306.6	17.8	GB	Basil	2
Y(+120.03)YHELLHGR	Q07473 CB4A _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1306.6	18.0	GB	Basil	1
EFLVLH(+105.04)LQFELDSLQGLAK	Q9XF88 CB4B _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	2476.3	22.3	HD	Basil	2
EVPLYH(+105.04)LQFDLDSLQNLAK	Q9XF88 CB4B _ARATH	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	2462.2	22.1	HD	Basil	2
H(+105.04)GVFLWSWFH(+105.04)WFDNCA GLSADEPTFAK	P08221 CB21 _CUCSA	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	3377.5	22.0	HD	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)GCDYLGPNPSLVVPAR	Q10HDO CB2 3_ORYSJ	Chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1842.9	20.4	GB	Basil	1
RY(+33.96)VVD DAGVLSR	P29357 HSP7 E_SPIOL	Chloroplast envelope membrane	1382.7	17.4	CI	Nettle	1
KLLRY(+120.03)LPGESDSDFDFSSK	Q9SA52 CP41 B_ARATH	Chloroplast stem-loop binding protein, chloroplastic	2410.1	19.2	GB	Laurel	1
KQPLAQKLY(+120.03)SDSDFDFSSK	Q9SA52 CP41 B_ARATH	Chloroplast stem-loop binding protein, chloroplastic	2410.1	19.5	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)LLKLPGESDSDFDFSSK	Q9SA52 CP41 B_ARATH	Chloroplast stem-loop binding protein, chloroplastic	2410.1	19.5	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)Y(+120.03)LLDVVYDLNGR	Q9SA52 CP41 B_ARATH	Chloroplast stem-loop binding protein, chloroplastic	1841.9	21.8	GB	Basil	1
VAVEAQWVADY(+120.03)AVK	Q0WLB5 CLA H2_ARATH	Clathrin	1667.8	17.8	GB	Basil	1
TPLTDAAAAY(+120.03)YRR	P25076 CY11 _SOLTU	Cytochrome	1587.8	19.7	GB	Laurel	1
H(+105.04)HLTFPLSPDPTTK	A6MMV7 CYF _ILLOL	Cytochrome	1807.9	21.8	HD	Basil	2
QFY(+120.03)SVTVESAEATLK	Q9SRZ6 ICDH C_ARATH	Cytosolic isocitrate dehydrogenase [NADP]	1791.9	18.5	GB	Laurel	1
GFVY(+120.03)DLLLLPR	F4JLP5 PLPD2 _ARATH	Dihydropyridyl dehydrogenase, chloroplastic	1424.8	22.8	GB	Basil	1
KYH(+105.04)VAEMNKR	P34824 EF1A 1_HORVU	Elongation factor	1379.7	15.3	HD	Laurel	1

LPLQDVY(+33.96)K	Q03033 EF1A_WHEAT	Elongation factor	1008.5	19.7	Cl	Nettle	1
DY(+120.03)LPGHKKLTLR	O24310 EFTU_PEA	Elongation factor, chloroplastic	1660.9	19.8	GB	Basil	1
KWSY(+120.03)LFAVEDVFSLTGR	Q43467 EFTU1_SOYBN	Elongation factor, chloroplastic	2137.1	23.4	GB	Basil	1
H(+105.04)LEAPSRLAAQPK	Q6ZA06 GUN20_ORYSJ	Endoglucanase	1634.9	20.1	HD	Laurel	1
ATLPAFY(+67.92)LKKLPLPLR	Q42971 ENO_ORYSJ	Enolase	1908.1	21.7	Cl	Nettle	1
KNEVHKY(+120.03)RDDTLLEDEELAK	P56337 IF5A5_SOLTU	Eukaryotic translation initiation factor	2506.2	20.3	GB	Basil	1
WPY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)LFDLFDDWLR	P23225 GLTB_MAIZE	Ferredoxin-dependent glutamate synthase, chloroplastic	2188.0	22.3	GB	Basil	1
NGY(+120.03)LSFLANLVLSDR	Q43155 GLTB_SPIOL	Ferredoxin-dependent glutamate synthase, chloroplastic	1800.9	21.0	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)VMAAEKPAADAPAAEPK	Q69RJ0 GLTB_ORYSJ	Ferredoxin-dependent glutamate synthase, chloroplastic	2020.0	17.7	GB	Basil	1
VVPLLEAY(+67.92)VPK	Q69RJ0 GLTB_ORYSJ	Ferredoxin-dependent glutamate synthase, chloroplastic	1294.6	20.5	Cl	Nettle	1
H(+105.04)DLLQLSGHDGGTGASPVSSLK	Q43155 GLTB_SPIOL	Ferredoxin-dependent glutamate synthase, chloroplastic	2280.1	18.7	HD	Basil	1
TY(+120.03)SNTGVKGA VNVQWDDK	P25851 F16P1_ARATH	Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase, chloroplastic	2114.1	19.1	GB	Laurel	1
H(+105.04)DELVLVFEHR	P46256 ALF1_PEA	Fructose-bisphosphate aldolase, cytoplasmic	1497.8	21.5	HD	Laurel	1
WKYWY(+120.03)VLKENNVLPGLK	P46256 ALF1_PEA	Fructose-bisphosphate aldolase, cytoplasmic	2269.2	21.3	GB	Basil	1
QECKH(+105.04)TDVLQENNVLPGLK	O65581 ALFC5_ARATH	Fructose-bisphosphate aldolase, cytosolic	2269.1	20.9	HD	Basil	1
RPLTY(+33.96)GLLLASLGLEWDNGGR	P16096 ALFC_SPIOL	Fructose-bisphosphate aldolase, cytosolic	2334.2	18.4	Cl	Nettle	1
Y(+120.03)Y(+120.03)LVFEVLQK	Q9XQ94 GLNA2_MEDSA	Glutamine synthetase leaf isozyme, chloroplastic	1540.8	15.8	GB	Basil	1
H(+105.04)KLLNLDVTPYTDK	O22506 GLNA2_DAUCA	Glutamine synthetase, chloroplastic	1760.9	21.3	HD	Basil	1
HPY(+120.03)LSAYGEDGKR	O22506 GLNA2_DAUCA	Glutamine synthetase, chloroplastic	1611.7	15.1	GB	Basil	1
QMY(+120.03)HVFEVLQK	O22506 GLNA2_DAUCA	Glutamine synthetase, chloroplastic	1540.8	15.9	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)WTPKGE GNER	O22506 GLNA2_DAUCA	Glutamine synthetase, chloroplastic	1611.8	15.1	GB	Laurel	1
KHKY(+67.92)WDELFGGYLYFHK	O24338 ASNS_SANAU	Glutamine-dependent asparagine synthetase	2298.0	21.0	Cl	Nettle	1
Y(+120.03)LVRHYPLDVVDFMR	P09044 G3PB_TOBAC	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase B, chloroplastic	2141.1	22.9	GB	Basil	1
HSMLGTFY(+120.03)ER	P09044 G3PB_TOBAC	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate, chloroplastic	1359.6	15.8	GB	Basil	1
LTLFGDKPVAVY(+33.96)GPR	P08735 G3PC1_MAIZE	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate, cytosolic	1665.9	22.1	Cl	Nettle	1
KGADVCH(+105.04)VVEAVR	O49954 GCSP_SOLTU	Glycine decarboxylase	1486.8	16.2	HD	Basil	1
WQQA AEKY(+120.03)RQPAAAEATAPVPK	P26969 GCSP_PEA	Glycine dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	2530.3	17.3	GB	Basil	1

Y(+33.96)AASDLRKAK	Q01899 HSP7 M_PHAVU	Heat shock protein, mitochondrial	1155.6	17.3	Cl	Nettle	1
MSY(+120.03)AFFADYTEAHLK	Q9FE01 APX2 _ORYSJ	L-ascorbate peroxidase, cytosolic	1912.8	20.6	GB	Basil	1
LAEEAAEKRY(+120.03)KPAAAEEDGVPAPK	P30184 AMPL 1_ARATH	Leucine aminopeptidase	2530.3	17.1	GB	Laurel	1
GY(+120.03)KLEGGGGPGLTK	O24248 PRU1 _PRUAV	Major allergen Pru av 1	1638.8	15.7	GB	Laurel	1
H(+105.04)PELEGGGGPGLTK	O24248 PRU1 _PRUAV	Major allergen Pru av 2	1510.7	16.4	HD	Basil	1
KRQQY(+120.03)VCTSELPPPR	O24248 PRU1 _PRUAV	Major allergen Pru av 3	1921.0	21.2	GB	Laurel	1
LYY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)VLRFESLKPSDIDLG SK	O49079 PSBO _FRIAG	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	2733.3	21.0	GB	Basil	1
LSEELGKGH(+105.04)AK	P14226 PSBO _PEA	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1401.7	15.5	HD	Basil	1
H(+105.04)EGPLEVSVLKDR	P85194 PSBO _HELAN	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1582.8	20.0	HD	Laurel	1
SEQWNVEVY	Q40459 PSBO _TOBAC	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1595.7	18.9	Cl	Nettle	1
H(+105.04)GENWLEYPGQVLR	P16059 PSBP _PEA	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1801.9	20.8	HD	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)MQWLEYPGQVLR	P16059 PSBP _PEA	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1801.9	21.1	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)WWWWEYPGKVLR	P85189 PSBP _HELAN	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1801.9	21.0	GB	Laurel	1
DGDATEH(+105.04)HKLLSATVNDGK	Q04127 PSBP 3_TOBAC	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	2112.0	16.4	HD	Basil	1
EAVH(+105.04)AH(+105.04)APSDELEYPGQV LR	Q04127 PSBP 3_TOBAC	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	2427.2	20.3	HD	Basil	1
SY(+120.03)NDELEYPGKVLR	Q04127 PSBP 3_TOBAC	Oxygen-evolving enhancer, chloroplastic	1801.9	21.2	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)CVTPNVVVAADNAAPPR	P83218 PME_ DAUCA	Pectinesterase	1976.0	20.1	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)TWASLAAEAKK	O49006 PME 3_ARATH	Pectinesterase	1457.7	18.8	GB	Laurel	1
HVVFGQVVEPY(+33.96)GLPK	Q39613 CYPH _CATRO	Peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase	1701.9	19.1	Cl	Nettle	1
QLVNY(+120.03)VGTEAVAK	P50318 PGKH 2_ARATH	Phosphoglycerate kinase, chloroplastic	1510.8	18.4	GB	Laurel	1
REVLPTTLVVADKFAY(+120.03)NSK	P41758 PGKH _CHLRE	Phosphoglycerate kinase, chloroplastic	2383.3	22.0	GB	Basil	1
HY(+120.03)VFAVGTEAVAK	Q42961 PGK H_TOBAC	Phosphoglycerate kinase, chloroplastic	1510.8	18.7	GB	Basil	1
H(+105.04)ELAGFQYLGPPETGEK	P0DKC3 PGP1 A_ARATH	Phosphoglycolate phosphatase, chloroplastic	1936.9	22.0	HD	Laurel	1
H(+105.04)MQEPLVVGALK	P0DKC3 PGP1 A_ARATH	Phosphoglycolate phosphatase, chloroplastic	1425.8	17.4	HD	Laurel	1
KFY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)DGTGLFQTLVGLK	P26302 KPPR _WHEAT	Phosphoribulokinase, chloroplastic	2189.1	22.3	GB	Basil	1
WLYGY(+33.96)CPYYHVSLEFDGQFDR	P26302 KPPR _WHEAT	Phosphoribulokinase, chloroplastic	2790.2	22.0	Cl	Nettle	1
WH(+105.04)EPAYGGPLFNPLGFGK	Q9SY97 LHCA 3_ARATH	Photosystem chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	2188.1	22.2	HD	Basil	1
KHY(+120.03)WALAPPELLGK	Q9SY97 LHCA 3_ARATH	Photosystem chlorophyll binding protein, chloroplastic	1644.9	21.7	GB	Basil	1
KTY(+120.03)HPLVYDTWESPK	P12372 PSAD _SOLLC	Photosystem I reaction center, chloroplastic	1983.0	20.3	GB	Laurel	1
RRNNVTEALH(+105.04)TYH(+105.04)YFYW PLFGGSTGGLLR	P36213 PSAD _HORVU	Photosystem I reaction center, chloroplastic	3634.8	22.3	HD	Basil	1

Y(+120.03)AHPADGLPHLLVSTAQR	P13192 PSAF_HORVU	Photosystem I reaction center, chloroplastic	2065.1	21.4	GB	Basil	1
AAEEAAEKY(+120.03)RKPAAAEATPVAPK	P12354 PSAE_SPIOL	Photosystem I reaction center, chloroplastic	2488.3	16.1	GB	Laurel	1
WSFAAEH(+105.04)HPENLLFPPEVLPR	Q2MIA5 PSB_D_SOLL	Photosystem II D2	2622.3	20.5	HD	Basil	2
AAEDPEFETFY(+33.96)TK	Q3MA59 PSB_D_TRIV2	Photosystem II D2	3877.4	20.7	Cl	Nettle	1
WKY(+120.03)VY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)PKSV GRATELNAVNYVSPR	P0C367 PSBC_ORYSJ	Photosystem II reaction center	3319.6	21.1	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)AEDGTLALAGR	Q09G50 PSBC_PLAOC	Photosystem II reaction center	1355.6	23.6	GB	Laurel	1
QRDLWHAPY(+67.92)KVLVGGVATELNAVNY VSPR	Q09G50 PSBC_PLAOC	Photosystem II reaction center	3319.6	21.0	Cl	Nettle	1
QSFDH(+105.04)TLAVGWLGHPLFR	P56777 PSBB_ARATH	Photosystem II reaction center	2185.1	21.1	HD	Basil	1
LMVVY(+33.96)ERTFPVVLVDGDGLVR	Q06FP2 PSBB_PELHO	Photosystem II reaction center	2410.2	22.5	Cl	Nettle	1
VPVY(+33.96)FETFPVVLVDGDGLVR	Q06FP2 PSBB_PELHO	Photosystem II reaction center	2254.1	22.7	Cl	Nettle	1
FVDPSDPLLDYF(+120.03)R	Q70XY1 PSBB_AMBTC	Photosystem II reaction center	1702.8	22.1	GB	Basil	1
GY(+120.03)HLGDGNAVGLGHPLFR	P56777 PSBB_ARATH	Photosystem II reaction center	2185.1	21.5	GB	Basil	1
VFDPSDPLLDYF(+120.03)R	P56777 PSBB_ARATH	Photosystem II reaction center	1702.8	22.1	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)FGKVEDEDFEFAGVDVSK	P11970 PLAS_2_POPNI	Plastocyanin B, chloroplastic	2555.2	20.1	GB	Laurel	1
ERP(+33.96)EFMLNAPGEVYVTLSEK	P00288 PLAS_VICFA	Plastocyanin	2592.2	21.4	Cl	Nettle	1
GPEVY(+33.96)PMYLNAPGEVYVTLSEK	P00288 PLAS_VICFA	Plastocyanin	2576.2	21.3	Cl	Nettle	1
KVY(+120.03)VS(+120.03)VVFDEDEVPARD VAK	P07030 PLAS_SILLB	Plastocyanin, chloroplastic	2667.3	19.3	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)CMTQDQEGVPEMTVPK	Q9FHQ6 UBQ_9_ARATH	Polyubiquitin	2173.9	20.4	GB	Laurel	1
LEGAYDRY(+33.96)FQLEAASQQFNGYELDGR	Q9JL3 PREP1_ARATH	Presequence protease 1, chloroplastic/mitochondrial	3073.4	22.2	Cl	Nettle	1
VVAEAAKAQFSNKAY(+120.03)YDK	Q2JRU4 AMP_A_SYNJA	Probable cytosol aminopeptidase	2122.0	17.4	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)RKMVMGLDKSLEAEFLDR	P83344 XYNB_PRUPE	Putative beta-D-xylosidase	2420.2	22.8	GB	Laurel	1
Y(+120.03)TLPGHKKAFLPR	P83344 XYNB_PRUPE	Putative beta-D-xylosidase	1646.9	18.6	GB	Laurel	2
Y(+120.03)HNHY(+120.03)LLVGQLEWR	P31414 AVP1_ARATH	Pyrophosphate-energized vacuolar membrane proton pump	2067.0	16.5	GB	Basil	1
MCVVY(+120.03)DLTDPFGLLTDHK	Q40521 RB11B_TOBAC	Ras-related protein Rab11B	2299.1	21.9	GB	Basil	1
RRKRY(+120.03)YVELSEVLYNR	P28644 ROC1_SPIOL	ribonucleoprotein, chloroplastic	2263.2	22.6	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)KDEAAPAKRPAEAPK	Q4FP12 RS16_PELUB	ribosomal protein	2017.1	15.8	GB	Basil	1
RKY(+120.03)ADAPAEAPK	O22518 RSSA_SOYBN	ribosomal protein	1435.7	15.7	GB	Basil	1
TPKFLEGGSVY(+120.03)ELVEK	Q4FG71 RR3_RANMC	ribosomal protein, chloroplastic	1915.0	19.6	GB	Laurel	1
AEERDKY(+120.03)RKPAAAEAPAEAPK	P24929 RK12_TOBAC	ribosomal protein, chloroplastic	2417.2	16.1	GB	Basil	1
VAY(+33.96)PIDLFEESVTNLFTSIVGNVFGFK	P48711 RBL_PICAB	RuBisCO	3096.5	23.0	Cl	Nettle	2

GHYLNATAATC(+67.92)EEMLKR	Q1KVVO RBL_ TETOB	RuBisCO	1974.8	16.2	Cl	Nettle	2
DY(+120.03)MEVHSGTVVGK	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1540.7	15.1	GB	Basil	1
EY(+120.03)FDPSGTVVGK	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1417.7	15.6	GB	Basil	1
MVENY(+120.03)KY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)DD ENVNSKPFMR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2901.2	19.0	GB	Basil	1
MWY(+120.03)VHSGTVVGQLEWR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2067.0	16.5	GB	Basil	1
TY(+120.03)WTKDDENVNSQPETR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2202.0	20.3	GB	Basil	1
WY(+120.03)MVHSGTVVGQLEWR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2067.0	16.5	GB	Basil	2
WY(+120.03)PDHSGTVVGKLEWR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2049.0	16.5	GB	Basil	1
NNAAQSH(+105.04)KWDLAAEGANLLR	P28420 RBL_ UNCGR	RuBisCO	2283.1	19.2	HD	Basil	1
LTYTPEY(+33.96)NPKDIDLAAFR	P28438 RBL_ PASQU	RuBisCO	2424.1	22.5	Cl	Nettle	1
LTYTPEY(+33.96)ETK	P48706 RBL_ LACSA	RuBisCO	1440.6	19.4	Cl	Nettle	2
MAVWTKH(+105.04)WYRSDVWTDGLTSLDR	Q33438 RBL_ ERYCG	RuBisCO	2927.4	20.6	HD	Basil	1
AVYY(+120.03)FLTAGREDDKTFDANSQPFMR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	3061.4	20.5	GB	Laurel	1
WY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)SGVNVVNSQPFMR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	2186.0	20.9	GB	Laurel	1
DEDNVNSQPFY(+33.96)DPK	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1700.7	18.9	Cl	Nettle	1
EAAATDAEALY(+33.96)K	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1285.6	22.7	Cl	Nettle	1
EEENVNSKPY(+33.96)PR	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1494.7	18.6	Cl	Nettle	1
Y(+67.92)TSASGLHAGTVVGK	P19163 RBL_ NEUMU	RuBisCO	1514.7	15.7	Cl	Nettle	1
RY(+120.03)MDTDLLAAFR	P48708 RBL_ MOROL	RuBisCO	1590.8	21.7	GB	Laurel	1
WY(+120.03)DHTAGAVEEMLKR	Q32303 RBL_ GALLU	RuBisCO	1924.9	17.8	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)HLLAQDR	Q33438 RBL_ ERYCG	RuBisCO	1192.6	17.0	GB	Basil	1
GY(+120.03)LADAASKEDLKAR	P21239 RUB1 BRANA	RuBisCO	1889.9	18.6	GB	Laurel	1
KKDCY(+120.03)RLLEELEQK	P34794 RUB2 BRANA	RuBisCO	1914.0	21.5	GB	Basil	1
KVY(+33.96)LSFLAYKFKDYR	P19310 RBS4 LEMGI	RuBisCO	1974.0	19.9	Cl	Nettle	1
H(+105.04)ELSEESLKEGK	Q08185 RBS5 MESCR	RuBisCO	1489.7	16.4	HD	Laurel	1
WRWY(+120.03)DVSDDKDLAR	O98997 RCA_ VIGRR	RuBisCO activase	2072.0	19.9	GB	Laurel	1
H(+105.04)WDYMLVQEQENVK	Q01587 RCA_ CUCSA	RuBisCO activase	1922.9	21.4	HD	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)NDEDKKTVDAATPK	Q40281 RCA_ MALDO	RuBisCO activase	1813.8	17.7	GB	Laurel	1
LY(+33.96)SEALGDANQDLAK	Q40281 RCA_ MALDO	RuBisCO activase	1711.8	19.5	Cl	Nettle	1
CY(+120.03)PEDPTAEGFYLAFFDK	Q7X9A0 RCA 1_LARTR	RuBisCO activase	2400.0	21.9	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)Y(+120.03)FLVQEQERGRK	Q7X9A0 RCA 1_LARTR	RuBisCO activase	2111.0	19.3	GB	Basil	1

Y(+120.03)AQVGKCLVQEQENVK	Q7X9A0 RCA1_LARTR	RuBisCO activase	1955.0	20.0	GB	Basil	1
Y(+120.03)TNTDRWNLLLEDVSDDKDLAR	Q7X9A0 RCA1_LARTR	RuBisCO activase	2786.3	20.9	GB	Basil	1
H(+105.04)GNLEDVSDDKQDLAR	Q7X999 RCA2_LARTR	RuBisCO activase	1915.9	20.9	HD	Laurel	1
KLVAVY(+33.96)DLNENANGLAR	A9P822 METK1_POPTR	S-adenosylmethionine	2093.1	19.3	Cl	Nettle	1
TADY(+67.92)RRHKLLSATVK	P09439 LOX2_SOYBN	Seed linoleate 9S-lipoxygenase-2	1825.9	16.4	Cl	Nettle	1
SSAKVAEY(+120.03)VKAK	Q94C74 GLYM2_ARATH	Serine hydroxymethyltransferase, mitochondrial	1399.7	16.0	GB	Basil	1
LDESTGYIDY(+33.96)DQLEK	P50433 GLYM_SOLTU	Serine hydroxymethyltransferase, mitochondrial	1821.8	18.7	Cl	Nettle	1
CPEAAEKY(+120.03)RKPAAAATVPAPK	Q940H6 SRK2E_ARATH	Serine/threonine-protein kinase	2417.2	16.1	GB	Basil	1
RDEAAEKY(+120.03)RQPAAAATVPAPK	Q940H6 SRK2E_ARATH	Serine/threonine-protein kinase	2488.2	16.2	GB	Basil	1
Y(+33.96)NLSLGLGLNK	P84187 SGAT_MAIZE	Serine--glyoxylate aminotransferase	1224.6	18.9	Cl	Nettle	2
H(+105.04)DVYMWVATANLLEESTPTVDGK	Q9THX6 TL29_SOLLC	Thylakoid lumenal, chloroplastic	2779.3	22.2	HD	Basil	1
KNQY(+120.03)LEAEWNAK	O20250 TKTC_SPIOL	Transketolase, chloroplastic	1612.8	17.8	GB	Laurel	2
YPRY(+120.03)NWTAGSYK	O20250 TKTC_SPIOL	Transketolase, chloroplastic	1624.7	16.0	GB	Basil	1
KHLNYMAAKSHNY(+33.96)LLGTGSELEAAK	Q8RWV0 TKTC1_ARATH	Transketolase, chloroplastic	3005.5	20.9	Cl	Nettle	1
SPEEAAEKY(+120.03)RKPAAAATVPAPK	F4IW47 TKTC2_ARATH	Transketolase, chloroplastic	2530.3	17.2	GB	Basil	1
RY(+120.03)KAKEVHSLCGGK	Q9M4S8 TPIC_FRAAN	Triosephosphate isomerase, chloroplastic	1694.9	18.9	GB	Basil	1

^a Peptides detected in given number of repetitions (N)

CHAPTER 7

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Biomarker profiling in plants to distinguish between exposure to chlorine gas and bleach using LC-HRMS/MS and chemometrics

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1. LC-MS/MS parameters

Table S 1. Chromatographic and mass spectrometric parameters for plant biomarkers analyzed by LC-MS/MS.

Analyte	Retention time (min)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)	Collision energy (eV)	Cone voltage (V)	Chemical structure
Cl-Tyr	6.3	216.2	170.3	15	10	
			135.3	25		
di-Cl-Tyr	6.7	250.1	204.0	15	10	
			169.0	30		
Cl-Phe	6.9	200.0	183.0	10	30	
			165.0			
			153.9			
Cl-Cyt	4.6	146.0	129.0	15	30	
			101.0	15		
			74.0	17		
Cl-Ade	5.9	170.0	133.8	15	30	
			107.0	20		
			80.0	22		
Cl-dopamine	5.7	188.0	171.0	7	30	
			153.0	10		
		171.0	125.0	17		
			89.0	22		
2Cl-dopamine	6.0, 6.7	222.0	205.0	8	30	
			159.0	12		
		205.0	159.0	20		
3Cl-dopamine	6.7	256.0	239.0	8	30	
		239.0	204.0	22		
			193.0	21		

2. Overview of tentatively identified biomarkers

Table S 2. Biomarkers tentatively identified by Compound Discover after LC-HRMS/MS analysis of green spire, stinging nettle and feathergrass after chlorine and bleach exposure. Chemicals are sorted by their molecular mass.

#	Name	Formula	Mass (g/mol)
1	AL8225000	C2 H2 Cl N	74.9876
2	Imidazole + Cl*	C3 H3 Cl N2	101.9985
3	H-beta-Chloro-Ala-OH	C3 H6 Cl N O2	123.0085
4	2-pyridone + Cl*	C5 H4 Cl N O	128.9981
5	Valerolactam + Cl*	C5 H8 Cl N O	133.0294
6	Pentanamide + Cl*	C5 H10 Cl N O	135.0451
7	Bis(2-chloroethyl)amine* [†]	C4 H9 Cl2 N	141.0110
8	SJ5700000	C6 H6 Cl N O	143.0136
9	2-Amino-5-chlorophenol	C6 H6 Cl N O	143.0138
10	2,4-Diamino-6-chloropyrimidine	C4 H5 Cl N4	144.0203
11	5-chlorocytosine	C4 H4 Cl N3 O	145.0043
12	Histamine + Cl*	C5 H8 Cl N3	145.0404
13	2-Pyrrolidone + 2Cl*	C4 H5 Cl2 N O	152.9748
14	p-Chloroacetophenone	C8 H7 Cl O	154.0183
15	2-Chlorobenzoic acid [§]	C7 H5 Cl O2	155.9977
16	2,4-Dichlorophenol	C6 H4 Cl2 O	161.9639
17	Valerolactam + 2Cl*	C5 H7 Cl2 N O	166.9904
18	2-Amino-6-chloropurine [‡]	C5 H4 Cl N5	169.0170
19	N1-(3-chlorophenyl)acetamide [§]	C8 H8 Cl N O	169.0291
20	NSC 444	C8 H8 Cl N O	169.0292
21	Tyramine + Cl*	C8 H10 Cl N O	171.0449
22	1-Methyl-1,4-dihydronicotinamide + Cl*	C7 H9 Cl N2 O	172.0402
23	2-amino-5-chloro-cis,cis-muconic 6-semialdehyde	C6 H6 Cl N O3	175.0036
24	cloxyquin	C9 H6 Cl N O	179.0137
25	Valine + 2Cl*	C5 H9 Cl2 N O2	185.0009
26	Guanine + Cl*	C5 H4 Cl N5 O	185.0105
27	4-CPA	C8 H7 Cl O3	186.0082
28	Dopamine + Cl*	C8 H10 Cl N O2	187.0398
29	DG6650000 [§]	C7 H4 Cl2 O2	189.9587
30	Acetyl proline + Cl*	C7 H10 Cl N O3	191.0346
31	Guvacine + 2Cl*	C6 H7 Cl2 N O2	194.9854
32	clominorex	C9 H9 Cl N2 O	196.0404
33	Fenclonine	C9 H10 Cl N O2	199.0397
34	Quinoclamine	C10 H6 Cl N O2	207.0086
35	6-Chloro-7-nitroquinoxaline ^{†,§}	C8 H4 Cl N3 O2	208.9992
36	Chlortoluron	C10 H13 Cl N2 O	212.0713
37	4-acetaminobutyric acid + 2Cl*	C6 H9 Cl2 N O3	212.9959
38	Carmustine	C5 H9 Cl2 N3 O2	213.0068

39	3-Chlorotyrosine	C9 H10 Cl N O3	215.0346
40	Dopamine + 2Cl*	C8 H9 Cl2 N O2	221.0009
41	ciproxime	C11 H8 Cl N O2	221.0243
42	4-(4-chlorophenoxy)-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole	C11 H11 Cl N2 O	222.0527
43	Arecoline + 2Cl*	C8 H11 Cl2 N O2	223.0164
44	seclazone	C10 H8 Cl N O3	225.0192
45	2-Chloro-N-(2,6-diethylphenyl)acetamide	C12 H16 Cl N O	225.0915
46	1-(3-Chloro-2-fluorophenyl)-3-(dimethylamino)prop-2-en-1-one	C11 H11 Cl F N O	227.0478
47	2-(2-chlorophenyl)-1H-indole ^{†,‡}	C14 H10 Cl N	227.6910
48	5-chloro-3-phenylbenzo[c]isoxazole	C13 H8 Cl N O	229.0262
49	Levodopa + Cl*	C9 H10 Cl N O4	231.0295
50	Ethychlozate	C11 H11 Cl N2 O2	238.0507
51	6-Chlorotryptophan [§]	C11 H11 Cl N2 O2	238.0508
52	bupropion	C13 H18 Cl N O	239.1088
53	2,4-DB [§]	C10 H10 Cl2 O3	248.0005
54	Val-Pro + Cl*	C10 H17 Cl N2 O3	248.0925
55	3,5-Dichlorotyrosine	C9 H9 Cl2 N O3	248.9957
56	Dopamine + 3Cl*	C8 H8 Cl3 N O2	254.9618
57	Lamotrigine	C9 H7 Cl2 N5	255.0062
58	Arecoline + 3Cl*	C8 H10 Cl3 N O2	256.9773
59	Traumatic Acid + Cl*	C12 H19 Cl O4	262.0968
60	Leu-Pro + Cl*	C11 H19 Cl N2 O3	262.1082
61	Moclobemide [§]	C13 H17 Cl N2 O2	268.0978
62	1-Hydroperoxy-L-tryptophan + Cl*	C11 H11 Cl N2 O4	270.0406
63	Medazepam	C16 H15 Cl N2	270.0888
64	Bupranolol	C14 H22 Cl N O2	271.1342
65	N2-(4-chlorophenyl)thiophene-2-carboxamide	C11 H8 Cl N O S	274.9519
66	N'-{6-[(5-chloro-3-pyridyl)oxy]-3-pyridyl}-N,N-dimethyliminoformamide	C13 H13 Cl N4 O	276.0815
67	Dibutyl malate + Cl*	C12 H21 Cl O5	280.1075
68	AE1300200	C14 H16 Cl N O3	281.0815
69	Val-Phe + Cl*	C14 H19 Cl N2 O3	298.1082
70	3-(3,4-dichlorobenzyl)-4H-1-benzothiazin-4-one [§]	C16 H10 Cl2 O S	319.9826
71	2-chloro-1,3,8-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)-9,10-dihydroanthracene-9,10-dione	C15 H9 Cl O6	320.0083
72	12-oxo-phytodienoic acid + Cl*	C18 H27 Cl O3	326.1644
73	A-12(13)-EpODE + Cl*	C18 H29 Cl O3	328.1801
74	2-[(2-chlorobenzyl)sulfanyl]-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile	C15 H13 Cl N2 S	343.0264
75	13(S)-HpOTrE + Cl*	C18 H29 Cl O4	344.1749
76	4-{3-[(5-chloro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)oxy]phenyl}morpholine	C17 H15 Cl N2 O2 S	346.0506
77	1-[3-(3,4-dichlorophenoxy)-2-hydroxypropyl]piperidine-4-carboxamide	C15 H20 Cl2 N2 O3	346.0870
78	Val-Trp + 2Cl*	C14 H18 Cl2 N2 O4	348.0638

79	doxepazepam	C17 H14 Cl F N2 O3	348.0663
80	N5-[2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-oxoethyl]-1-ethyl-3-methyl-4-nitro-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxamide†	C15 H15 Cl N4 O4	350.0784
81	(Z)-4-Chloro-N-(3-ethoxy-1-hydroxy-3-oxopropylidene)tryptophan	C16 H17 Cl N2 O5	352.0829
82	9,12,13-Trihydroxy-10,15-octadecadienoic acid + Cl*	C18 H31 Cl O5	362.1854
83	N1-(1-benzyl-4-piperidyl)-4-chlorobenzene-1-sulfonamide	C18 H21 Cl N2 O2 S	364.0974
84	Metolazone§	C16 H16 Cl N3 O3 S	365.0589
85	(4-chlorophenyl)[4,6-dimethyl-3-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)thieno[2,3-b]pyridin-2-yl]methanone	C20 H15 Cl N2 O S	366.0582
86	4-{5-[(3S)-1-(4-Chlorobenzyl)-3-pyrrolidinyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-N,N-dimethylaniline†	C21 H23 Cl N4 O	382.1514
87	Dibutyl sebacate + 2Cl*	C18 H32 Cl2 O4	382.1671
88	13S-hydroxyoctadecadienoic acid + 3Cl*	C18 H29 Cl3 O3	398.1175
89	Pinellic acid + 2Cl*	C18 H32 Cl2 O5	398.1620
90	N-{6-[(7-chloro-4-quinazolinyloxy)-3-pyridinyl]-4-methoxybenzamide	C21 H15 Cl N4 O3	406.0879
91	N2-({(1S,3S,4R,5R)-3-[(3-chloro-4-fluorobenzoyl)amino]-1,4,5-trihydroxycyclohexyl}carbonyl)-D-leucinamide†	C20 H27 Cl F N3 O6	419.1644
92	Phloionolic acid + 3Cl*	C18 H33 Cl3 O5	434.1387
93	(1S,2R,3S,5S,6S,16E,18E,20R,21S)-11-Chloro-21-hydroxy-12,20-dimethoxy-2,5,16-trimethyl-8,23-dioxo-4,24-dioxo-9,22-diazatetracyclo[19.3.1.1~10,14~.0~3,5~]hexacos-10(26),11,13,16,18-pentaen-6-yl 2-methylpropanoate	C31 H41 Cl N2 O9	620.2500

*Chemicals are also identified in unchlorinated form in the blank vegetation samples.

†Chemicals are not present in all plant species

‡Chemical is only detected in bleach samples

§Chemical is only detected in chlorinated samples

3. Machine learning analysis

Figure S 1. Explained variance of PCA with effect of leave-one-group-out validation on PCA robustness. Green line: PCA including all samples; blue dashed lines: PCAs with one type of exposure left out: without A) short, B) long, and C) high chlorine exposure, and without D) household, E) pool, and F) concentrated bleach exposure.

Figure S 2. LDA-score plot for classification of plants exposed to chlorine gas or bleach and unexposed plants ($n = 12-38$). Corresponding LDA scores for the first and second discriminant function are shown. The bars represent the frequency of the individual measurements for a given LDA value adding up to 1. The shaded curve is the kernel density estimation with a bandwidth of 1. Ten principal components (accounting for 97% of the variation) were used to build the LDA model.

Figure S 3. LDA value to likelihood ratio (LR) plot with and without artificially reducing the empirical upper and lower bound (ELUB) of the LR values. ELUB values are $6.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to 12. Figure corresponds to Figure 4 of the manuscript.

Figure S 4. Tippet plots showing the cumulative likelihood ratio (LR) distributions calculated with LDA for chlorine and bleach exposed samples, measured by LC-HRMS/MS. A) Without correction. B) With ELUB correction. The dashed lines show $LR = 1$.

Figure S 5. LDA-score plot for classification of plants exposed to low, mid, or high chlorine gas and household, pool, or concentrated bleach (n=9-18). Corresponding LDA scores for the first and second discriminant function are shown. A-C) Training sets, D) test set *Euonymus*, E) test set grass, F) test set nettle.

Figure S 6. PCA-loading plot. PC1 represents 23% of the total variance and PC2 accounts for 14% of the variance. Some of the most discriminating compounds are highlighted. 1. Medazepam; 8. 4-(4-chlorophenoxy)-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole; 16. 2-Chlor-N-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)-N-(2-oxotetrahydro-3-furanyl)acetamid; 21. 2-Chlorobenzoic acid; 23. Valine + 2Cl; 33. 6-Chlorotryptophan; 34. Chlortoluron; 36. Carmustine; 59. 5-chlorocytosine; 67. 2,4-Dichlorophenol; 78. 1-Hydroperoxy-L-tryptophan + Cl; 82. Dopamine + 2Cl; 85. Fenclonine; 87. Dopamine + 3Cl; 88. Dopamine + Cl; 90. 3-Chlorotyrosine; 92. 3,5-Dichlorotyrosine.

4. LC-MS/MS chromatograms

Figure S 7. Extracted ion chromatograms of 3-chlorotyrosine (Cl-Tyr, $t_R = 5.70$ min, m/z 216.2 \rightarrow 170.3) and 3,5-dichlorotyrosine (di-Cl-Tyr, $t_R = 6.26$ min, m/z 250.1 \rightarrow 204.0). A) Commercially available reference standard, B) Nettle exposed to concentrated bleach, C) Nettle exposed to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 8. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 146.0 \rightarrow 129.0) of 5-chlorocytosine (Cl-Cyt) with $t_R=4.58$ min. A) Commercially available reference standard, B) Nettle exposed to concentrated bleach, C) Nettle exposed to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 9. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 188.0 \rightarrow 171.0) of chlorodopamine (Cl-dopamine) with $t_R=5.24$ and 5.70 min. A) Synthetic reference standard, B) Nettle exposed to concentrated bleach, C) Nettle exposed to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 10. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 239.0 \rightarrow 204.0) of trichlorodopamine (tri-Cl-dopamine) with $t_R=6.70$ min. A) Synthetic reference standard, B) Nettle exposed to concentrated bleach, C) Nettle exposed to a high concentration chlorine.

4.1. Stability

Figure S 11. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 146.0 \rightarrow 129.0) of 5-chlorocytosine (Cl-Cyt) with $t_R=4.56$ min. A) Commercially available reference standard, B) Nettle, three months after exposure to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 12. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 170.0 \rightarrow 107.0) of 2-amino-6-chloropurine (Cl-Ade) at $t_R=5.82$ min. A) Commercially available reference standard, B) Nettle, three months after exposure to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 13. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 222.0 \rightarrow 205.0) of dichlorodopamine (di-Cl-dopamine) at $t_R=5.92$ and 6.63 min. A) Synthetic reference standard, B) Nettle, three months after exposure to a high concentration chlorine.

Figure S 14. Extracted ion chromatograms (m/z 239.0 \rightarrow 204.0) of trichlorodopamine (tri-Cl-dopamine) with $t_R=6.70$ min. A) Synthetic reference standard, B) Nettle, three months after exposure to a high concentration chlorine.

5. NMR spectra

¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at 400 MHz. A concentration of approximately 1 mg/mL was analysed. DMSO-d₆ was used as a solvent (2.5 ppm) and some water was present in the sample (4-3 ppm).

The figures below show the measured NMR spectrum of dopamine, Cl-dopamine, di-Cl-dopamine, and tri-Cl-dopamine. Together with the measured spectrum, the predicted spectrum is also presented. The peaks within a chemical shift of 6 and 7 originate from the aromatic part of the chemical. Two doublets and one doublet of doublets were visible in dopamine, corresponding to three protons in total. After chlorination the number of peaks reduced to two (Cl-dopamine), one (2Cl-dopamine) or zero (3Cl-dopamine) singlets. The responses from the aliphatic part of the chemical were visible around 3 ppm and the peaks around 9 ppm originate from the alcohols. The amine is known to give a broader, but less intense peak that exhibits shifts in the spectrum [1]. Therefore, the peak between 7 and 8 ppm most likely corresponds to the amine. In every spectrum three impurity peaks are visible around 7 ppm. This presumably originates from 3-methoxytyramine [2], a metabolic product of dopamine.

The chemical shifts and ratios of the measured spectra of unchlorinated, mono-, di-, and tri-chlorinated dopamine correspond well to the predicted NMR spectra (Mnova 14.3.3., Mestrelab Research) and published spectra [3–5]. Only, for Cl-dopamine the predicted spectrum was not shown, since it was different compared to the NMR spectrum presented by Garcia-Fernandez et al. [4]. In literature, the isomer 4-(2-aminoethyl)-5-chloro-1,2-benzenediol showed two singlets in the aromatic region, while the other isomers show ortho or meta coupling for the substituted benzene ring [3]. In this study, also two singlets were visible, so Cl-dopamine was most likely identified as 4-(2-aminoethyl)-5-chloro-1,2-benzenediol. Both purified peaks in the LC-MS chromatogram provided a similar NMR spectrum without ortho or meta coupling, so it was not possible to identify the various isomers. Therefore, an unspecific representation of the isomers was provided in this study and future research is needed to unravel the exact structure of the chlorinated dopamines.

Figure S 15. NMR spectrum of dopamine. A) Measured NMR spectrum. B) Predicted NMR spectrum.

Figure S 16. Measured NMR spectrum of Cl-dopamine (corresponds to LC-MS/MS t_R : 5.70).

Figure S 17. NMR spectrum of di-Cl-dopamine (corresponds to LC-MS/MS t_R : 5.96). A) Measured NMR spectrum. B) Predicted NMR spectrum.

Figure S 18. NMR spectrum of di-Cl-dopamine (corresponds to LC-MS/MS t_R : 6.66). A) Measured NMR spectrum. B) Predicted NMR spectrum.

Figure S 19. NMR spectrum of tri-Cl-dopamine (corresponds to LC-MS/MS t_R : 6.7). A) Measured NMR spectrum. B) Predicted NMR spectrum.

6. LC-HRMS/MS isotope ratios

Figure S 20. Full scan MS spectrum analyzed by LC-HRMS/MS of single charged chlorinated dopamine showing the chlorine isotope pattern. A) Dopamine, B) Single chlorination of dopamine with an isotope ratio of 3:1, C) Double chlorination of dopamine with an isotope ratio of 9:6:1, and D) Triple chlorination with an isotope ratio of 27:26:9:1.

Because the ^{35}Cl isotope has a natural occurrence of 76% and the ^{37}Cl isotope of 24%, the isotope ratio for the chlorinated compound can be calculated. The isotope value for mono-, di- and tri-chlorinated dopamine is measured including the effect of other isotopes such as ^{13}C . [6] In Table S3 the theoretical isotope value is compared to the measured isotopes values in the synthetic reference standard and nettle plants exposed to chlorine gas.

Table S 3. Comparison of theoretical versus experimentally observed isotope values in full scan MS spectrum as obtained with LC-HRMS/MS for chlorinated dopamine.

Chlorination	Theoretical isotope value	Measured isotope value in synthetic reference standard	Measured isotope value in nettle
0	1	1	1
1	3:1	3:1	3:1
2	9:6:1	9:6:1	9:6:1
3	27:27:9:1	27:26:9:2	27:27:9:3

Table S 4. Theoretical versus measured monoisotopic mass of chlorinated dopamine isotopes in full scan MS spectrum as obtained with LC-HRMS/MS.

Cl	Isotope	Theoretical monoisotopic mass	Measured monoisotopic mass in synthetic reference standard	Mass error (ppm)	Measured monoisotopic mass in nettle plant	Mass error (ppm)
0	[M+H] ⁺	154.0868	154.0861	5	154.0862	4
1	[M+H+35Cl-H] ⁺	188.0478	188.0472	3	188.0469	5
1	[M+H+37Cl-H] ⁺	190.0449	190.0439	5	190.0442	4
2	[M+H+2*35Cl-2H] ⁺	222.0089	222.0078	5	222.0083	2.7
2	[M+H+35Cl+37Cl-2H] ⁺	224.0059	224.0053	2.7	224.0050	4
2	[M+H+2*37Cl-2H] ⁺	226.0030	226.0024	2.7	226.0022	4
3	[M+H+3*35Cl-2H] ⁺	255.9699	255.9694	2.0	255.9695	1.6
3	[M+H+2*35Cl+37Cl-3H] ⁺	257.9669	257.9663	2.3	257.9664	1.9
3	[M+H+35Cl+2*37Cl-3H] ⁺	259.9640	259.9629	4	259.9639	0.4
3	[M+H+3*37Cl-2H] ⁺	261.9610	261.9606	1.5	261.9606	1.5

7. LC-HRMS/MS mass spectra

Figure S 21. HRMS/MS spectrum of nettle exposed to chlorine gas with fragmentation pattern of A) Dopamine (m/z 154.0861), B) Cl-dopamine (m/z 188.0472), C) di-Cl-dopamine (m/z 222.0084), and D) tri-Cl-dopamine (m/z 255.9694).

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CHAPTER 8

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary Information

A novel standard for forensic elemental profiling of polymers by LA-ICP-TOF-MS

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1. Forensically relevant polymer objects

Table S 1. Information of wires, tubing, jerrycans and tapes analyzed by LA-ICP-MS and FT-IR.

#	Type	Supplier	Brand	Color	Details	Production date	Polymer type*
86	Wire	Wholesale	Draka	Black	Vinyl (VD)	n.a.	PVC-P
87	Wire	Wholesale	Eldra	Blue	0.75 mm ² , Eca fire class.	n.a.	PVC-P
88	Wire	Wholesale	LTC	Brown	0.75 mm ² , Lead free label	n.a.	PVC-P-NBR
89_y**	Wire	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-green	2.5 mm ² , Yellow part	n.a.	PVC-P
89_g**	Wire	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-green	2.5 mm ² , Green part	n.a.	PVC-P
90	Wire	Hornbach	Q-link	Grey	0.35 mm ²	n.a.	PVC-U-GF
91_f***	Tubing	Wholesale	Pipelife	Grey	3/4 inch", polivalit, Front side	15-7-2013, 06:37	PVC-U
91_b***	Tubing	Wholesale	Pipelife	Red	3/4 inch", polivalit, Back side	15-7-2013, 06:37	Bunatex K71
92_f***	Tubing	Wholesale	Pipelife	Yellow	5/8", 'polivolt, Front side	18-10-2013, 17:11	PVC-U
92_b**	Tubing	Wholesale	Pipelife	Yellow-orange	5/8", 'polivolt, Back side	18-10-2013, 17:11	PVC-U
93	Tubing	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	3/4", Low Friction	28-3-2013, 11:16	PVC-U-GF/ PVC-U-ABS
94	Tubing	Praxis	Martens	White	3/4"	25-8-2020, 23:12	PVC-Hard
95	Tubing	Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Grey	5/8"	20-9-2021, 23:54	PVC-U
96	Jerrycan	Hornbach	Hünersdorff	Red	811400, Tube	n.a.	LDPE
97	Jerrycan	ANWB	ANWB	Black	10802598, Can	n.a.	HDPE
98	Jerrycan	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Blue	970700, Can	n.a.	HDPE
99	Jerrycan	Bol	All Ride, Meno Berlin	Yellow	2514278, Tube	n.a.	HDPE
100	Jerrycan	Bol	Claudius Cosmetics B.V.	White	B042, Can	n.a.	HDPE/LDPE
101	Tape	Hornbach	Hornbach	Blue	n.a.	n.a.	PVC-P
102	Tape	Karwei	Karwei	Red	n.a.	n.a.	PVC-P-NBR
103	Tape	Hornbach	Coroplast	Brown	n.a.	n.a.	PVC-P
104_y**	Tape	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-Green	Yellow part	n.a.	PVC-P-NBR/PVC-P
104_g**	Tape	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-Green	Green part	n.a.	PVC-P-NBR/PVC-P
105	Tape	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Black	Label Coroplast	n.a.	PVC-P

*Identified by FT-IR

**The object consisted of two colors yellow (y) and green (g)

*** The tube had a different inner layer, so the front (f) and the back (b) were measured

2. Detailed production method of polymer standards

Table S 2. Added chemicals to polymer standards with correction for total molecular weight.

Element	Chemical	M (g/mol)	M _{element} (g/mol)	M% Element	ρ (g/mL)	Stock 5 mg/mL*
23 Na	Sodium ethanolate	68.05	22.99	0.34		14.8
24 Mg	Magnesium chloride	95.21	54.94	0.58		8.7
27 Al	Aluminium triisopropylate	204.24	26.98	0.13		37.8
29 Si	Tetraethyl orthosilicate	208.33	28.09	0.13	0.93	37.1
39 K	Potassium permanganate	158.03	39.10	0.25		20.2
44 Ca	Calcium chloride dihydrate	147.01	40.08	0.27		18.3
49 Ti	Titanium(IV)isopropoxide	284.22	47.87	0.17	0.96	29.7
52 Cr	Chromium(III)chloride hexahydrate	266.45	52.00	0.20		25.6
55 Mn	Potassium permanganate	158.03	54.94	0.35		14.4
57 Fe	Iron(III)nitrate nonahydrate	404.00	55.85	0.14		36.2
59 Co	Cobalt(II)chloride, hexahydrate	237.93	58.93	0.25		20.2
60 Ni	Nickel(II)acetate tetrahydrate**	248.84	58.69	0.24		21.2
63 Cu	Copper(II)acetate	181.63	63.55	0.35		14.3
69 Ga	Gallium(III) acetylacetonate	367.05	69.72	0.19		26.3
75 As	Arsenic (III) chloride	181.28	74.92	0.41	2.16	12.1
88 Sr	Strontium tetramethylheptanedionate	454.15	87.62	0.19		25.9
90 Zr	Zirconium(IV) butoxide solution 80 wt	383.68	91.22	0.30	1.05	16.8
93 Nb	Tetrachlorobis(tetrahydrofuran)niobium	378.93	92.91	0.25		20.4
105 Pd	(bis(triphenylphosphine)Pd(II)dichloride	701.90	106.42	0.15		33.0
118 Sn	Tin(II) 2-ethylhexanoate	405.12	118.71	0.29	1.25	17.1
121 Sb	Antimony pentafluoride	216.75	121.76	0.56	2.99	8.9
137 Ba	Barium bis(2-ethylhexanoate)	423.73	137.32	0.32		15.4
208 Pb	Lead tetra acetate	443.36	207.20	0.47		10.7

*This column shows the total concentration of the chemical consisting of multiple atoms which is needed to obtain a concentration of 5 mg/mL for the element of interest.

Various volumes of the stock solution presented in Table S2 were added to the standard solutions to obtain different elemental concentrations as shown in Table S3. For the middle and low concentration standards, lower stock solutions of 0.5 and 0.05 mg/mL were made.

Table S 3. Applied elemental concentrations in the low, middle, and high concentration PE, PS and PVC standard.

Element	PE (mg/kg)			PS (mg/kg)			PVC (mg/kg)		
	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High
Na23	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500
Mg24	40	200	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Al27	200	400	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Si28	100	200	2000	50	100	1000	50	100	1000
K39	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Ca44	1000	1500	2000	50	200	1000	10	100	1000
Ti47	20	20	2000	500	5	500	10	100	1000
Cr53	20	100	200	10	50	200	5	50	500
Mn55	2.8	28	280	1.4	14	140	1.4	14	140
Fe56	2	20	200	5	50	500	2	20	200
Co59	1	10	100	0.1	1	10	0.2	2	20
Ni60	1	10	100	0.5	5	50	0.2	2	20
Cu63	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500
Ga71	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
As75	2	20	200	0.5	5	50	5	50	500
Sr88	4	40	400	1	10	100	1	10	100
Zr90	0.04	0.4	40	0.02	0.2	20	0.02	0.2	20
Nb93	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Pd105	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Sn118	2	20	200	1	10	100	2	20	200
Sb121	10	100	1000	5	50	500	20	200	1000
Ba137	10	100	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Pb208	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500

3. Design of experiments

Table S 4. Design of experiments used for method optimization to limit the number of measurements.

RunOrder	Mixing time (hours)	Drying temperature (°C)	Polymer
1	48	50	PS
2	24	20-22	PVC
3	18	50	PS
4	24	20-22	PS
5	18	2-8	PE
6	18	20-22	PS
7	18	50	PE
8	18	20-22	PE
9	24	50	PVC
10	4	2-8	PVC
11	24	50	PE
12	4	20-22	PVC
13	48	20-22	PS
14	24	20-22	PE
15	6	50	PVC
16	6	2-8	PVC
17	48	20-22	PE
18	24	2-8	PE

Figure S 1. Pareto Chart of Standardized Effects. The factors mixing time (A), temperature (B) and polymer type (C) were included. The red reference line indicates statistically significant effects with $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure S 2. Fitted line plot of the effect of A) Temperature and B) Mixing time on the homogeneity (%RSD). No significant correlation was observed.

4. Produced standards and forensic objects

Figure S 3. Small pieces of blanks, standards and forensic polymer objects of approximately 5x5 mm for LA-ICP-TOF-MS analysis. 49-51: PE Blank, 52-54: PS blank, 55-57: PVC blank, 58-60: PE low, 61-63: PS low, 64-66: PVC low, 67-69: PE mid, 70-72: PS mid, 73-75: PVC mid, 76-79: PE high, 80-82: PS high, 83-85: PVC high, 86-90 wires, 91-95: tubing, 96-100: jerrycans, 101-105: tapes.

Figure S 4. Magnification with a diameter of approximately 500 μm of new polymer standards. 49-51: PE Blank, 52-54: PS blank, 55-57: PVC blank, 58-60: PE low, 61-63: PS low, 64-66: PVC low, 67-69: PE mid, 70-72: PS mid, 73-75: PVC mid, 76-79: PE high, 80-82: PS high, 83-85: PVC high.

5. LA-ICP-TOF-MS line scans

Figure S 5. Three consecutive LA-ICP-TOF-MS line scans over a distance of 1 mm for a) PE, b) PS and c) PVC standards with elements in the concentration range of 10 – 1000 mg/kg polymer. Dashed lines mark the start and end of a line scan.

Figure S 6. Three consecutive LA-ICP-TOF-MS line scans over a distance of 1 mm of ten most abundant elements in A) an electrical wire, B) PVC tubing, C) jerrycan and D) tape. Dashed lines mark the start and end of a line scan.

6. Linearity

Figure S 7. Calibration curves of responses in counts per seconds (CPS) of PE, PS and PVC with an elemental concentration ranging from 0 to 1000 mg/kg analyzed by LA-ICP-TOF-MS.

7. XRF analysis

Table S5 shows the elemental concentrations measured by XRF. Sodium (Na) was not included due to a detection limit of 2000 mg/kg, which exceeded the applied concentrations.

Table S 5. Comparison of applied elemental concentrations in PE, PS and PVC standards with concentrations analyzed by XRF.

Element	PE			PS			PVC		
	Applied (mg/kg)	Measured (mg/kg)	Deviation (%)	Applied (mg/kg)	Measured (mg/kg)	Deviation (%)	Applied (mg/kg)	Measured (mg/kg)	Deviation (%)
Mg24	1000	405	-63	500	1528	206	500	482	-4
Si28	2000	2104	5	1000	1573	57	1000	798	-20
K39	200	119	-41	100	375	275	100	101	1
Ca44	2000	1632	-18	1000	3891	289	1000	530	-47
Ti47	2000	1466	-27	500	1642	228	1000	441	-56
Cr53	200	191	-4	200	477	138	500	263	-47
Mn55	280	183	-35	140	263	88	140	88	-37
Fe56	200	180	-10	500	937	87	200	102	-49
Co59	100	77	-23	10	17	69	20	14	-30
Ni60	100	65	-35	50	77	53	20	13	-34
Cu63	200	149	-25	100	131	31	500	245	-51
Ga71	200	169	-16	100	128	28	100	34	-66
As75	200	183	-9	50	70	39	500	291	-42
Sr88	400	300	-25	100	105	5	100	59	-41
Nb93	200	169	-16	100	105	5	100	83	-17
Pd105	200	163	-19	100	97	-3	100	88	-12
Sn118	200	151	-25	100	118	18	200	132	-34
Sb121	1000	500	-50	500	280	-44	1000	505	-49
Ba137	1000	1019	2	500	893	79	500	428	-14
Pb208	200	179	-11	100	125	25	500	304	-39

8. Classification with overlap criteria

Figure S 8. Box plot of mean elemental responses with correction for new reference standards for wires from seven different suppliers and brands. The minimum and maximum value are ± 2 * stdv. (n=36).

Figure S 9. Box plot of mean elemental responses with correction for new reference standards for tubing from seven different suppliers and brands. The minimum and maximum value are ± 2 * stdv. (n=36).

Figure S 10. Box plot of mean elemental responses with correction for new reference standards for jerrycans from five different suppliers and brands. The minimum and maximum value are ± 2 * stdv. (n=36).

CHAPTER 9

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary data

Evaluating the strength of evidence of elemental profiling of polymers with LA-ICP-MS

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1. Elemental concentrations of polymer standards

Table S1. Applied elemental concentrations in the low, middle, and high concentration PE, PS, and PVC standard.

Element	PE (mg/kg)			PS (mg/kg)			PVC (mg/kg)		
	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High	Low	Mid	High
Na23	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500
Mg24	40	200	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Al27	200	400	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Si28	100	200	2000	50	100	1000	50	100	1000
K39	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Ca44	1000	1500	2000	50	200	1000	10	100	1000
Ti47	20	20	2000	500	5	500	10	100	1000
Cr53	20	100	200	10	50	200	5	50	500
Mn55	2.8	28	280	1.4	14	140	1.4	14	140
Fe56	2	20	200	5	50	500	2	20	200
Co59	1	10	100	0.1	1	10	0.2	2	20
Ni60	1	10	100	0.5	5	50	0.2	2	20
Cu63	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500
Ga71	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
As75	2	20	200	0.5	5	50	5	50	500
Sr88	4	40	400	1	10	100	1	10	100
Zr90	0.04	0.4	40	0.02	0.2	20	0.02	0.2	20
Nb93	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Pd105	2	20	200	1	10	100	1	10	100
Sn118	2	20	200	1	10	100	2	20	200
Sb121	10	100	1000	5	50	500	20	200	1000
Ba137	10	100	1000	5	50	500	5	50	500
Pb208	2	20	200	1	10	100	5	50	500

2. Information forensically relevant polymer objects

Tapes from 82 different brands/suppliers (referred to as: 'Source') were evaluated. For three tapes three batches (A, B, C) of the same Source were investigated (64, 72, 82). In addition, five tapes consisted of two colors. To make the data analysis more convenient, the original number was kept for the green colored part of the tapes. The yellow parts were numbered 83-87 instead of 7, 25, 29, 39, and 45. The tapes mainly consisted of plasticized PVC (PVC-P).

Table S1. Information of tapes analyzed by LA-ICP-MS and FT-IR, obtained from various suppliers.

#	Supplier/country	Brand	Color	Details	Polymer type*
1	Hornbach	Hornbach	Yellow		PVC-P
2	Hornbach	Hornbach	Red		PVC-P
3	Hornbach	Hornbach	Green		PVC-P
4	Hornbach	Hornbach	Blue		PVC-P
5	Hornbach	Hornbach	Black		PVC-P
6	Hornbach	Hornbach	White		PVC-P
7	Karwei	Karwei	Yellow-Green		PVC-P-NBR
8	Karwei	Karwei	Blue		PVC-P-NBR
9	Karwei	Karwei	Black		PVC-P-NBR
10	Karwei	Karwei	White		PVC-P-NBR
11	Karwei	Karwei	Red		PVC-P-NBR
12	Hornbach	Coroplast	Purple		PVC-P
13	Hornbach	Coroplast	Yellow		PVC-P
14	Hornbach	Coroplast	Brown		PVC-P
15	Hornbach	Coroplast	Grey		PVC-P
16	Hornbach	Coroplast	Red		PVC-P
17	Hornbach	Coroplast	Blue		PVC-P
18	Hornbach	Coroplast	Orange		PVC-P
19	Hornbach	Coroplast	Black		PVC-P
20	Hornbach	Coroplast	White		PVC-P
21	Hornbach	Coroplast	Green		PVC-P
22	Gamma	Handson	Brown		PVC-P-NBR
23	Gamma	Handson	Black		PVC-P-NBR
24	Gamma	Handson	Blue		PVC-P-NBR
25	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-Green		PVC-P
26	Gamma	Handson	Red		PVC-P-NBR
27	Gamma	Handson	Black		PVC-P-NBR
28	Gamma	Handson	White		PVC-P-NBR
29	Gamma	Handson	Yellow-Green		PVC-P-NBR/PVC-P
30	Gamma	Tesa	Black	5mx50mm	PVC-P-NBR
31	Gamma	Tesa	Red	10mx15mm	PVC-U
32	Gamma	Tesa	Black	10mx15mm	PVC-U
33	Praxis	GS International	Green	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
34	Praxis	GS International	White	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
35	Praxis	GS International	Black	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
36	Praxis	GS International	Blue	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
37	Praxis	GS International	Yellow	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
38	Praxis	GS International	Red	10mx18mm	PVC-P-NBR
39	Praxis	Tesa	Yellow-Green	10mx15mm	PVC-P-NBR
40	Praxis	Tesa	White	20mx50mm	PVC-P
41	Praxis	Tesa	Red	20mx50mm	PVC-P
42	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Black	20mx19mm	PVC-P
43	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Green	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
44	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Black	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
45	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Yellow-Green	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
46	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Grey	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
47	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Blue	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
48	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Brown	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
49	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Yellow	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
50	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Orange	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
51	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	Red	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P

52	Praxis	Heinrich Kopp	White	10mx15mm, Coroplast imprint	PVC-P
53	Lowe	Utilitech	Black	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
54	Lowe	Utilitech	White	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
55	Lowe	Utilitech	Green	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
56	Lowe	Utilitech	Blue	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
57	Lowe	Utilitech	Yellow	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
58	Lowe	Utilitech	Red	1/2inx10ftx7mil	-
59	USA	3M	Black	Scotch 700 Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
60	USA	3M	Black	Scotch Heavy Duty Vinyl Electrical Tape 22	-
61	USA	3M	Black	Scotch Super 33+ Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
62	USA	3M	Black	Scotch Super 88 Professional Grade Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
63	Poland	3M	Black	Temflex 165 General Use Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
65	Poland	3M	Black	Temflex 175 General Use Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
66	USA	3M	Black	Temflex General Use Vinyl Electrical Tape 1776	-
67	Taiwan	Amazon	Black	Amazon Commercial Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
68	China	DiversiTech	Black	Morris General Purpose Vinyl Electrical Tape 60000	-
69	China	DiversiTech	Black	Morris Premium + Vinyl Electrical Splicing Tape 60110	-
70	China	DiversiTech	Black	Morris Premium Vinyl Electrical Splicing Tape 60100	-
71	Taiwan	Intertape Polymer Group	Black	Economy Grade Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
73	Taiwan	NSI	Black	WarriorWrap Black General Electrical Tape WW-716	-
74	Taiwan	NSI	Black	WarriorWrap Premium Vinyl Electrical Tape WW-732	-
75	Taiwan	NSI	Black	WarriorWrap Select Vinyl Electrical Tape WW-722	-
76	China	Shurtape	Black	Duck Brand Economy Electrical Tape 282289	-
77	China	Shurtape	Black	Duck Brand Professional Electrical Tape 393119	-
78	China	Shurtape	Black	Duck Heavy Duty Electrical Tape 393120	-
79	China	Shurtape	Black	EV 097 Premium Grade Vinyl Electrical Tape 104697	-
80	China	Shurtape	Black	EV 57 General Purpose Electrical Tape	-
81	China	Shurtape	Black	EV 77 Professional Grade Vinyl Electrical Tape 104706	-
64_A	USA	3M	Black	Temflex 1700 Vinyl Electrical Tape 5 pk	-
64_B	USA	3M	Black	Temflex 1700 Vinyl Electrical Tape 5 pk	-
64_C	USA	3M	Black	Temflex 1700 Vinyl Electrical Tape 5 pk	-
72_A	Taiwan	NSI	Black	Easy-Wrap Electrical Tape EWG7060 10 pk	-
72_B	Taiwan	NSI	Black	Easy-Wrap Electrical Tape EWG7060 10 pk	-
72_C	Taiwan	NSI	Black	Easy-Wrap Electrical Tape EWG7060 10 pk	-
82_A	China	Utilitech	Black	10 CT Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
82_B	China	Utilitech	Black	10 CT Vinyl Electrical Tape	-
82_C	China	Utilitech	Black	10 CT Vinyl Electrical Tape	-

Tubing from 36 different brands/suppliers (referred to as: 'Source') were evaluated. For source 1-3 also the inner part with a red coating was analyzed and numbered 37-39.

Table S2. Information of tubing analyzed by LA-ICP-MS and FT-IR, obtained from various suppliers.

#	Supplier	Brand	Color	Details	Polymer type*
1	wholesale	Pipelife	Grey	8712603060146	PVC-U (back: bunatex K71)
2	wholesale	Pipelife	Yellow	8712603054015	PVC-U-ABS (back: bunatex K71)
3	wholesale	Pipelife	Yellow	8712603054008	PVC-U
4	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	1 1/4	PVC-U
5	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	8712148067884	PVC-U
6	wholesale	Wavin	Yellow	1 1/4	PVC-U
7	wholesale	Univolt	White	3/4	PP
8	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	8712148067945	PVC-U
9	wholesale	Wavin	Creme	12X1	PVC-U
10	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	8712148067976	PVC-U
11	wholesale	Wavin	Grey	8712148512353	PVC-U-GF/ PVC-U-ABS (graphite fibril)
12	wholesale	-	Yellow		PVC-U-ABS
13	wholesale	-	White	1 1/4	PVC-U-GF
14	Praxis	Martens	Grey	32mm	PVC-Hard
15	Praxis	Martens, ecomar®	Grey	40mm	PVC-U-ABS
16	Praxis	Martens	White	32mm	PVC-Hard
17	Praxis	Martens	White	40mm	PVC-Hard
18	Praxis	Martens, ecomar®	Grey	50mm	PVC-Hard
19	Praxis	Martens	Yellow	8711422090945	PVC-U
20	Praxis	Martens	Yellow	8711422090969	PVC-Hard
21	Praxis	Martens	Grey	8711422107780	PVC-U
22	Praxis	Martens	Grey	8711422090990	PVC-U
23	Praxis	Martens	White	8711422189809	PVC-Hard
24	Praxis	Martens	White	8711422189779	PVC-Hard
25	Gamma	Pipelife, Akonyl	Grey	8716507000192	PVC-Hard
26	Gamma	Pipelife, Akonyl	Grey	8716507000239	PVC-Hard
27	Gamma/Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Yellow	8716507000024	PVC-U
28	Gamma/Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Yellow	8716507000086	PVC-Hard
29	Gamma/Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Yellow	8716507000024	PVC-U
30	Gamma/Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Yellow	8716507000086	PVC-U-ABS
31	Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Grey	8716507000147	PVC-U
32	Hornbach	Pipelife, Akonyl	Grey	8716507000161	PVC-U
33	Lowe	Charlotte Pipe	Yellow	PLNC 12005	-
34	Lowe	Silver-Line	White	PVC-1120	-
35	Lowe	Cantex	White	Schedule 40 rigid	-
36	Lowe	Charlotte Pipe	White	TrueFit system	-
37	wholesale	Pipelife	Red	8712603060146	PVC-U (back: bunatex K71)
38	wholesale	Pipelife	Red	8712603054015	PVC-U-ABS (back: bunatex K71)
39	wholesale	Pipelife	Red	8712603054008	PVC-U

Wires from 44 different brands/suppliers (referred to as: 'Source') were evaluated. For five sources the wires were colored with yellow-green stripes. The yellow part was considered as a separate sample and numbered 45-49.

Table S3. Information of wires analyzed by LA-ICP-MS and FT-IR, obtained from various suppliers.

#	Supplier	Brand	Color	Details	Polymer type*
1	wholesale	Nexans	Green		PVC-P-NBR
2	wholesale	Draka	Grey		PVC-P-NBR
3	wholesale	Ramcro	Red(-Black)		PVC-U-GF
4	wholesale	Ramcro	(Red-)Black		PVC-U-GF
5	wholesale	Draka	Black		PVC-P
6	wholesale	Draka	Blue		PVC-P
7	wholesale	Eldra	Blue		PVC-P
8	wholesale	Eldra	Brown		PVC-P
9	wholesale	Draka	Black		PVC-P
10	wholesale	Eldra	White		PVC-P
11	wholesale	Eldra	Green		PVC-P
12	wholesale	Draka	Red		PVC-P-NBR
13	wholesale	LTC	Brown	Lead free	PVC-P-NBR
14	wholesale	LTC	Red		PVC-P-NBR
15	wholesale	LTC	Orange	Lead free	PVC-P-NBR
16	Praxis	Sencys	Black		PVC-P
17	Praxis	Sencys	Brown		PVC-P
18	Praxis	Sencys	Blue		PVC-P
19	Praxis	Sencys	Green		PVC-P
20	Gamma	Handson	Black		PVC-P
21	Gamma	Handson	Grey		Ca(OH)2/ Silicone
22	Gamma	Handson	Blue		PVC-P
23	Gamma	Handson	Green		PVC-P
24	Gamma	Handson	White		PVC-U-GF
25	Hornbach	Q-link	Blue		Ca(OH)2/ Silicone
26	Hornbach	Q-link	Black		Ca(OH)2/ Silicone
27	Hornbach	Q-link	Black		PVC-P-NBR
28	Hornbach	Q-link	Brown		PVC-U-GF
29	Hornbach	Q-link	Blue		PVC-U-GF
30	Hornbach	Q-link	Green		PVC-U-GF
31	Hornbach	Q-link	White	HangZhou Xingfra Technology	PVC-P-NBR
32	Hornbach	Q-link	Grey		PVC-U-GF
33	Wholesale	Draka	Blue		PVC-P-NBR
34	Gamma	Handson	Red		PVC-U-ABS
35	Gamma	Handson	Blue		Polybutylene Terephthalate/PVC-U-ABS
36	Hornbach	Q-link	Red	HangZhou Xingfra Technology	HDPE
37	Hornbach	Q-link	Black	HangZhou Xingfra Technology	HDPE
38	Lowe	Southwire	Black		-
39	Lowe	Southwire	Green		-
40	Lowe	Southwire	Red		-
41	Lowe	Southwire	White		-
42	Lowe	Southwire	Transparent		-
43	Lowe	Southwire	Black		-
44	Lowe	Southwire	Brown		-
45	wholesale	Nexans	Yellow	Same wire as 1	PVC-P-NBR
46	wholesale	Eldra	Yellow	Same wire as 11	PVC-P
47	Praxis	Sencys	Yellow	Same wire as 19	PVC-P
48	Gamma	Handson	Yellow	Same wire as 23	PVC-P
49	Hornbach	Q-link	Yellow	Same wire as 30	PVC-U-GF

Jerrycans from 13 different brands/suppliers were evaluated. Most jerrycans consisted of several parts, such as the jerrycan, cap, cap pin, and filling tube. These parts were considered separately resulting in 39 samples.

Table S4. Information of jerrycans analyzed by LA-ICP-MS and FT-IR, obtained from various suppliers.

#	Set	Part	Supplier	Brand	Color	Details	Polymer type*
1	1	Can	Gamma	Carpoint	Black	3H1/Y1.2/150/21/ A/PA-03/200164/PLASTIK	HDPE
2	1	Cap	Gamma	Carpoint	Black	3H1/Y1.2/150/21/ A/PA-03/200164/PLASTIK	HDPE
3	1	Tube	Gamma	Carpoint	Yellow	3H1/Y1.2/150/21/ A/PA-03/200164/PLASTIK	LDPE
4	1	Cap pin	Gamma	Carpoint	Red	3H1/Y1.2/150/21/ A/PA-03/200164/PLASTIK	Polyoxymethylene (acetal) POM
5	2	Can	Hornbach	Hünersdorff	Black	3H1/Y1.0/150/ 21 /D/BAM 14026-huen	HDPE
6	2	Cap	Hornbach	Hünersdorff	Red	3H1/Y1.0/150/ 21 /D/BAM 14026-huen	LDPE
7	2	Tube	Hornbach	Hünersdorff	Red	3H1/Y1.0/150/ 21 /D/BAM 14026-huen	LDPE
8	3	Can	ANWB	ANWB	Black	3H1/Y1.2/150/2020 I/CSI89920DEU05	HDPE
9	3	Cap	ANWB	ANWB	Red	3H1/Y1.2/150/2020 I/CSI89920DEU05	PP (ELTEC P HP-603)
10	3	Tube	ANWB	ANWB	Red	3H1/Y1.2/150/2020 I/CSI89920DEU05	HDPE
11	3	Line	ANWB	ANWB	Black	3H1/Y1.2/150/2020 I/CSI89920DEU05	HDPE
12	4	Can	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Blue	3H1/Y1.9/200/21/NL/WIVA 3224	HDPE
13	4	Cap	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Black	3H1/Y1.9/200/21/NL/WIVA 3224	HDPE
14	5	Can	Bol	All Ride, RPC Promens Jagtenberg, Heerewaarden (NL)	Black	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP-090122	HDPE
15	5	Cap	Bol	All Ride, Meno Berlin	Yellow	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP-090122	HDPE
16	5	Tube	Bol	All Ride, Meno Berlin	Yellow	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP-090122	HDPE
17	6	Can	Bol	Claudius Cosmetics B.V.	Transparent	P.20.101	HDPE/LDPE
18	6	Cap	Bol	Claudius Cosmetics B.V.	White	P.20.101	HDPE/LDPE
19	7	Can	Bol	All Ride, Jagtenberg Plastics BV (NL)	Red	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP 110199	LDPE/HDPE
20	7	Cap	Bol	All Ride, Meno Berlin	Black	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP 110199	HDPE/LDPE
21	7	Tube	Bol	All Ride, Meno Berlin	Black	3H1/Y1.0/200/B/HJP 110199	LDPE
22	8	Can	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Blue	3H1/X1.9/250/B/AST-927805	HDPE
23	8	Cap	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Black	3H1/X1.9/250/B/AST-927805	HDPE
24	9	Can	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	White	7434213316314	HDPE
25	9	Cap	Bol	Splashbox Product Support B.V.	Black	7434213316314	HDPE
26	10	Can	Bol	EDA Plastiques	Blue	19554	HDPE
27	10	Cap	Bol	EDA Plastiques	Red	19554	PP

28	10	Tube	Bol	EDA Plastiques	Yellow	19554	LDPE/HDPE
29	11	Can	Bol	Amacoo B.V.	Red	3H1/Y/160/ 20 D/BAM11486-PDD	HDPE
30	11	Cap	Bol	Amacoo B.V.	Black	3H1/Y/160/ 20 D/BAM11486-PDD	HDPE
31	11	Tube	Bol	Amacoo B.V.	Black	3H1/Y/160/ 20 D/BAM11486-PDD	HDPE/LDPE
32	11	Cap pin	Bol	Amacoo B.V.	Red	3H1/Y/160/ 20 D/BAM11486-PDD	Polyoxymethylene (acetal) POM
33	12	Can	Bol	Moralisto, malmarks Hungary	Red	3H1/X1.2/250*/H 6YS-01- 01483-1-18	HDPE
34	12	Cap	Bol	Moralisto, malmarks Hungary	Black	3H1/X1.2/250*/H 6YS-01- 01483-1-18	LDPE/HDPE
35	12	Tube	Bol	Moralisto, malmarks Hungary	Black	3H1/X1.2/250*/H 6YS-01- 01483-1-18	LDPE/HDPE
36	13	Can	Bol	Hecht, J.P Plast, Werco spol.s r.o.	Black	3H1/Y/120/CZ/JPP-IMET 9031	HDPE
37	13	Cap	Bol	Hecht, J.P Plast, Werco spol.s r.o.	Red	3H1/Y/120/CZ/JPP-IMET 9031	LDPE
38	13	Tube	Bol	Hecht, J.P Plast, Werco spol.s r.o.	Red	3H1/Y/120/CZ/JPP-IMET 9031	LDPE
39	3	Fill Line	ANWB	ANWB	Transparent	3H1/Y1.2/150/21/ A/PA- 03/200164/PLASTIK	HDPE

3. Feature-based MVK model

For the evaluation of glass evidence various statistical models can be used. The feature-based multivariate Kernel (MVK) model (or two-level model) is currently in use at the Netherlands Forensic Institute for forensic glass casework and the utility of this method is demonstrated by various research groups in an interlaboratory study [1]. In this model, the elemental profile of a questioned sample will be compared to a control sample and all samples in the background database. The result will be a continuous likelihood ratio (LR), which is defined as the probability of the evidence given H_1 divided by the probability of the evidence given H_2 (equation 1). The prosecutor's hypothesis (H_1) for comparison problems is the proposition that two samples originate from the same source, while the defense hypothesis (H_2) is expressed as two samples having different sources. When the LR of a variable is considered statistically independent, the LR of variable A can be multiplied by the LR of variable B. When variables might be related, such as various physical characteristics or the elemental composition, the combined LR can be calculated [2].

$$LR = \frac{f(E|H_1)}{f(E|H_2)}$$

Equation 1

The MVK model will now be applied to a database consisting of 87 tapes from different sources with $n=8$ repetitions, containing the response of $p = 9$ elements measured by LA-ICP-MS. Table S6 shows how the database looks like. The mean concentration of 8 repetitions is given by \bar{x}_i where i represents each source.

Table S5. Part of normalized database of tapes measured by LA-ICP-MS ($n = 8, m=87$).

Source (m)	n	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
1	1	0.02	-1.63	1.51	-2.01	-1.31	-0.52	-0.62	-1.67	-2.31
	2	-0.09	-1.71	1.43	-2.04	-1.49	-0.60	-0.71	-1.77	-2.33
	3	0.01	-1.63	1.50	-2.00	-1.31	-0.48	-0.63	-1.77	-2.32
	4	-0.09	-1.70	1.46	-2.03	-1.46	-0.60	-0.70	-1.72	-2.45
	5	0.02	-1.64	1.47	-2.02	-1.32	-0.50	-0.63	-1.63	-2.36
	6	-0.01	-1.61	1.46	-1.97	-1.33	-0.55	-0.62	-1.69	-2.35
	7	-0.11	-1.73	1.45	-2.06	-1.52	-0.62	-0.72	-1.91	-2.41
	8	-0.06	-1.71	1.42	-1.96	-1.53	-0.71	-0.71	-1.68	-2.54
2	1	-0.37	-1.65	1.59	-2.43	-1.25	-0.42	-0.58	-1.62	-2.60
...
86	8	2.26	-2.20	0.89	-1.48	-0.89	-0.65	-1.10	0.60	-1.81
87	1	1.93	-1.62	1.52	-1.74	-1.00	1.13	-0.91	-1.00	-2.45
	2	1.94	-1.67	1.54	-1.69	-0.99	1.15	-0.91	-1.02	-2.53
	3	1.91	-1.71	1.51	-1.44	-1.00	1.12	-0.92	-1.01	-2.58
	4	1.87	-1.75	1.43	-1.78	-1.09	1.07	-0.96	-1.07	-2.55
	5	1.90	-1.61	1.44	-1.89	-1.07	1.10	-1.02	-1.03	-2.46
	6	1.93	-1.69	1.50	-1.75	-1.06	1.14	-0.99	-1.03	-2.59
	7	1.89	-1.74	1.46	-1.81	-1.11	1.09	-1.02	-1.07	-2.52
	8	1.87	-1.77	1.44	-1.59	-1.13	1.08	-1.07	-1.09	-2.49

3.1. Normalization

Prior to the likelihood ratio calculation, the data was normalized to the elemental response of ^{13}C . and a logarithmic transformation (\log_{10}) was applied to bring the data closer to normality and reduce stochastic measurement fluctuations [3]. Figure S1 shows the effect of the log transformation on the data.

Figure S1. Effect of \log_{10} transformation on the LA-ICP-MS data of tapes. A) Raw data. B) Data after normalization.

3.2. Same-source comparison

Subsequently, we first apply a same-batch comparison, where we select one sample from the database, and we separate it into a control and a recovered sample (ground truth: samples come from the same source). The control has $n_1 = 4$ repetitions with mean elemental concentrations of \bar{y}_1 . The recovered sample has $n_2=4$ repetitions with mean elemental concentrations of \bar{y}_2 . The resulting background database will now have 86 (87-1) sources. The mean of four replicates of the control sample (\bar{y}_1) is shown in Table S7. and the mean of the recovered sample (\bar{y}_2) is shown in Table S8.

Table S6. Mean of four replicates of the control sample.

Source (m)	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
1	-0.04	-1.67	1.48	-2.02	-1.39	-0.55	-0.67	-1.73	-2.35

Table S7. Mean of four replicates of the recovered sample.

Source (m)	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
1	-0.04	-1.67	1.45	-2.00	-1.42	-0.60	-0.67	-1.73	-2.42

3.3. Variance-covariance matrix

Since, we are aiming to express the evidential value in a single LR value, the features should be combined in a certain way. To gain knowledge about how the data is distributed, it is important to assess the within-object and between-object variability. For meaningful forensic comparisons it is important that the between-object variability is significantly larger than the within-object variability. One way to express the spread in the data is by calculating the variance (square root of this value is the commonly applied standard deviation). When more than one variable is included, a measure for the joint variability is required. This can be expressed by the covariance, which is a measure of the dependence of two variables. Table S9 and S10 show the variance-covariance matrices for within source distribution (**U**) and between source distribution (**C**). Since the result is symmetric, only the upper right triangle of the matrix is shown. The within source variation was calculated for all 86 samples separately and afterwards the mean matrix was used for the LR calculation. For the between source variation, the mean of each source in the background database was calculated and then the covariance of all the 86 samples was computed. The matrices show that the within source variation is much smaller than the between source variation. A graphical presentation of the correlation between pairs is shown in Figure S2. The diagonal shows the distribution of elemental concentrations found for a single element.

Table S8. Variance-covariance matrix for within source distribution of tape samples in background dataset.

	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
Al27	4.0E-03	7.4E-04	8.1E-04	2.1E-03	5.2E-04	1.0E-03	1.9E-03	3.6E-03	-5.5E-04
As75		1.3E-02	3.0E-06	2.8E-03	1.3E-04	2.5E-04	1.9E-03	7.4E-03	2.4E-03
Ca44			1.3E-03	4.5E-04	8.7E-04	8.5E-04	7.5E-04	1.8E-03	-5.6E-05
Cu63				4.8E-02	8.9E-04	1.9E-04	2.7E-03	5.4E-03	1.6E-03
Fe57					2.6E-03	7.9E-04	7.6E-04	2.0E-03	3.2E-04
Mg25						1.6E-03	6.5E-04	1.6E-03	1.3E-04
Pb208							5.0E-03	3.8E-03	9.8E-04
Si29								4.2E-02	4.1E-03
Sn118									1.7E-02

Table S9. Variance-covariance matrix for between source distribution of tape samples in background dataset.

	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
Al27	5.6E-02	5.1E-03	4.7E-03	5.3E-02	6.6E-03	7.8E-03	2.2E-02	-2.7E-03	-9.0E-02
As75		7.8E-04	9.2E-04	-3.1E-02	1.1E-03	1.1E-03	3.1E-03	-1.8E-04	-1.2E-02
Ca44			1.2E-03	-5.2E-02	1.4E-03	1.2E-03	3.5E-03	-1.2E-04	-1.3E-02
Cu63				4.1E+00	-5.2E-02	-3.2E-02	-1.0E-01	-9.8E-03	3.3E-01
Fe57					1.6E-03	1.5E-03	4.3E-03	-2.2E-04	-1.7E-02
Mg25						1.5E-03	4.2E-03	-3.0E-04	-1.7E-02
Pb208							1.2E-02	-8.2E-04	-4.7E-02
Si29								1.4E-04	3.6E-03
Sn118									1.9E-01

Figure S1. Graphical representation of the correlation between pairs of variables between sources of tape.

3.4. Kernel density estimation

It is assumed that the within source sample variation follows a normal distribution. However, the between source variation might not always be normally distributed. Therefore, the between source distribution is fitted by a Kernel density estimation (KDE). This is a method to estimate the probability density function of a variable using individual kernels (or curves) that are combined. The smoothing parameter (h) of the KDE can be calculated by equation 2 [4]. The combination of h with the between covariance is the kernel bandwidth matrix: $\mathbf{H} = h^2\mathbf{C}$.

$$h = \left(\frac{4}{m(2p+1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p+4}}$$

Equation 2

The general kernel density function for multivariate data ($\boldsymbol{\theta}$) is expressed as follows and can be recognized in the final LR calculation.

$$K(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i, \mathbf{H}) = (2\pi)^{-\frac{p}{2}} |\mathbf{H}|^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\theta} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i)^T \mathbf{H}^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\theta} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i) \right\}$$

Equation 3

3.5. Likelihood ratio

The numerator of the LR simulates that the control and recovered sample originate from the same source. Therefore, the difference in $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_1$ and $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_2$ is expressed by the weighted mean $\bar{\mathbf{y}}^*$ in equation 4. In addition, the rarity of the data is expressed by the distance from the mean $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i$ from the weighted mean $\bar{\mathbf{y}}^*$ [3].

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* = \frac{n_1\bar{\mathbf{y}}_1 + n_2\bar{\mathbf{y}}_2}{n_1 + n_2}$$

Equation 4

For the calculation of the LR it is important to consider specific rules for matrix algebra. All matrices and vector parameters are shown in **bold**. The numerator $f(E|H_1)$ of the LR for multivariate data is expressed in equation 5 below. The determinant of a matrix function is a scalar value that can be calculated based on the individual entries of a square matrix. In the exponent, the transpose of a vector with length 1 x p multiplied by a matrix of p x p results in a vector of length 1 x p. This is then multiplied by a vector with length p x 1, which gives a final dimension of 1 x 1, which will be a scalar. Consequently, the result of the numerator will be a single value which consists of the combined data of the features.

$$f(E|H_1) = (2\pi)^{-\frac{p}{2}} \times \det \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1} + \frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}_1 - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_2)^T \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1} + \frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_2} \right)^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}_1 - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_2) \right\} \times \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ (2\pi)^{-\frac{p}{2}} \times \det \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1+n_2} + h^2\mathbf{C} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i)^T \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1+n_2} + h^2\mathbf{C} \right)^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i) \right\} \right\}$$

Equation 5

The denominator $f(E|H_2)$ is calculated by equation 6. The first part describes the control (n_1, \bar{y}_1) characteristics and the second part shows the same equation for the recovered samples (n_2, \bar{y}_2). Also in this case, the result is a scalar value.

$$f(E|H_2) = (2\pi)^{-\frac{p}{2}} \times \det\left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1} + h^2\mathbf{C}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \times \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\bar{y}_1 - \bar{x}_i)^T \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1} + h^2\mathbf{C}\right)^{-1} (\bar{y}_1 - \bar{x}_i) \right\} \\ \times (2\pi)^{-\frac{p}{2}} \times \det\left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_2} + h^2\mathbf{C}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \times \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\bar{y}_2 - \bar{x}_i)^T \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_2} + h^2\mathbf{C}\right)^{-1} (\bar{y}_2 - \bar{x}_i) \right\}$$

Equation 6

For our specific example, the numerator is $6.2 \cdot 10^4$ and the denominator is $3.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$. This results in an LR of $1.7 \cdot 10^{10}$. Therefore, the evidence is extremely more probable if the samples originate from the same source than when the samples originate from different sources. The calculation can be performed for the entire database, to evaluate the rate of misleading evidence. If an LR smaller than one was calculated, this would have been a false negative result. The total number of same source pairs equals the database size with m number of groups. It should be noted that more comparisons can be made if all n repetitions are considered separately instead of using mean \bar{y}_1 and \bar{y}_2 .

3.6. Different-source comparison

A similar calculation can be performed for different-source comparisons. Sample 1 was considered as the control sample with $n_1=4$ repetitions and mean \bar{y}_1 (Table S11). Sample 2 was the reference sample with $n_2=4$ repetitions and mean \bar{y}_2 (Table S12). The resulting background database will now have 85 (87-2) sources.

Table S10. Mean of eight replicates of the control sample.

Source (m)	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
1	-0.04	-1.67	1.48	-2.02	-1.39	-0.55	-0.67	-1.73	-2.35

Table S11. Mean of eight replicates of the recovered sample.

Source (m)	Al27	As75	Ca44	Cu63	Fe57	Mg25	Pb208	Si29	Sn118
2	-0.34	-1.70	1.55	-2.49	-1.31	-0.55	-0.65	-1.72	-2.53

The numerator of the LR is calculated to be $8.5 \cdot 10^{-72}$ and the denominator is $2.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$. This results in an LR of $4.0 \cdot 10^{-66}$. Therefore, the evidence is extremely more probable if the samples originate from different sources than when the samples originate from the same source. This calculation can be performed for the entire database, to evaluate the rate of misleading evidence. If an LR larger than one was calculated, this would have been a false positive result. The total number of different source pairs can be calculated by equation 7 for background data with m groups. Because the comparison of source 1 with source 2 equals the comparison of source 2 with source 1, the total number of comparisons can be divided by 2. In this specific example 3741 different source pairs can be compared. It should be noted that a lot more comparisons can be made if not the average value of 4 repetitions of the sources is used.

$$\frac{1}{2} m(m-1)$$

Equation 7

3.7. Example with limited dataset

Since the calculation of the LR iterates over each background sample, it is a lengthy task to calculate it without programming. To get a feeling how the calculation is performed, the normalized database was reduced to four sources and two variables with four repetitions (Table S13). The elements Al and Pb were selected. Each step of the LR calculation is shown in the following sections.

Table S12. Limited dataset of tapes measured by LA-ICP-MS ($n = 8, m=4$).

Source (m)	n	Al27	Pb208
1 (control)	1	0.02	-0.62
	2	0.01	-0.63
	3	-0.09	-0.71
	4	-0.09	-0.70
1 (recovered)	5	0.02	-0.63
	6	-0.01	-0.62
	7	-0.11	-0.72
	8	-0.06	-0.71
2	1	-0.37	-0.58
	2	-0.38	-0.58
	3	-0.46	-0.70
	4	-0.45	-0.70
3	1	-0.10	-0.59
	2	-0.06	-0.57
	3	-0.15	-0.72
	4	-0.14	-0.72
4	1	-0.69	-0.80
	2	-0.64	-0.76
	3	-0.63	-0.89
	4	-0.26	-0.89

We apply a same-batch comparison, where we select sample 1 from the database, and we separate it into a control and a recovered sample (ground truth: samples come from the same source). The control has $n_1 = 4$ repetitions with mean elemental concentrations of \bar{y}_1 . The recovered sample has $n_2=4$ repetitions with mean elemental concentrations of \bar{y}_2 . The resulting background database will now have 3 (4-1) sources. The mean of four replicates of the control sample (\bar{y}_1), the mean of the recovered sample (\bar{y}_2), the weighted mean (\bar{y}^*) and the means of background samples \bar{x}_1 (source 2), \bar{x}_2 (source 3), and \bar{x}_3 (source 4) are shown in Table S14. For the background samples the mean of the first four replicates was calculated.

Table S13. Means of 4-8 replicates of sample analyzed by LA-ICP-MS.

Sample	Variable	Al27	Pb208
Control	\bar{y}_1	-0.04	-0.67
Recovered	\bar{y}_2	-0.04	-0.67
Weighted mean	\bar{y}^*	-0.04	-0.67
Background	\bar{x}_1	-0.42	-0.64
Background	\bar{x}_2	-0.11	-0.65
Background	\bar{x}_3	-0.56	-0.84

Subsequently, the within (co)variance matrix can be calculated for each background sample. The mean value of these matrices (**U**) is used for further calculations (Table S15). Also, the between (co)variance matrix (**C**) can be calculated (Table S16) based on the mean concentrations for each background sample from Table S14.

Table S14. Variance-covariance matrices for within source distribution of tape samples in background dataset.

		Al27	Pb208
2	Al27	0.0022	0.0032
	Pb208		0.0046
3	Al27	0.0018	0.0034
	Pb208		0.0069
4	Al27	0.0383	-0.0077
	Pb208		0.0042
average	Al27	0.0141	-0.0004
	Pb208		0.0052

Table S15. Variance-covariance matrix for between source distribution of tape samples in background dataset

		Al27	Pb208
2	Al27	0.0512	0.0180
	Pb208		0.0123

The following variables depicted in Table S17 are required for the LR calculation. The smoothing parameter is calculated based on Equation 2.

Table S16. Variables for LR calculation with limited dataset.

Variable	Value	Information
n	4	Number of repetitions background
n₁	4	Number of repetitions control
n₂	4	Number of repetitions recovered
m	3	Number of sources
p	2	Number of elements
h	0.802	Smoothing parameter KDE

All values can now be implemented in equations 5 and 6 to calculate the LR of equation 1. Each term of equation 5 is shown below.

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= (2\pi)^{-\left(\frac{p}{2}\right)} = 0.1592 \\
B &= \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1} + \frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_2}\right) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.0071 & -0.0002 \\ -0.0002 & 0.0026 \end{pmatrix} \\
D &= (\bar{\mathbf{y}}_1 - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_2) = (0.0022 \quad 0.0055) \\
E &= \left(\frac{\mathbf{U}}{n_1 + n_2} + h^2 \mathbf{C}\right) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.0347 & 0.0116 \\ 0.0116 & 0.0086 \end{pmatrix} \\
F &= \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_1)^T (\mathbf{E})^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_1)\right) = -4.63 \\
G &= \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_2)^T (\mathbf{E})^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_2)\right) = -0.317 \\
H &= \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_3)^T (\mathbf{E})^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{y}}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_3)\right) = -3.86 \\
I &= \det(\mathbf{B})^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} = (1.84 \times 10^{-5})^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} = 233 \\
J &= \det(\mathbf{E})^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} = (1.63 \times 10^{-4})^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} = 78.2 \\
K &= \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{D})^T (\mathbf{B})^{-1} (\mathbf{D})\right\} = 0.9937
\end{aligned}$$

Result numerator:

$$\begin{aligned}
f(E|H_1) &= A \times I \times K \times \frac{1}{m} \times \sum_{i=1}^m \{A \times J \times (\exp\{F\} + \exp\{G\} + \exp\{H\})\} \\
&= 0.1592 \times 233 \times 0.9937 \times \frac{1}{3} \\
&\quad \times \sum_{i=1}^3 \{0.1592 \times 78.2 \times (\exp\{F\} + \exp\{G\} + \exp\{H\})\} \\
&= 12.3 \times (12.4 \times (9.72 \times 10^{-3} + 7.28 \times 10^{-1} + 2.10 \times 10^{-2})) = 116
\end{aligned}$$

Equation 8

For the limited dataset, this will result in a numerator of 116 and a denominator of 10.5 which is calculated using equation 6 in a similar way as shown above. The uncalibrated LR will then be 11. Therefore, the evidence is more probable if the samples originate from the same source than when the samples originate from different sources.

4. LA-ICP-MS method optimization

4.1. Spot ablations of mid concentration samples

Figure S3 shows the effect of the laser energy on the counts and RSD for various spot sizes. As expected, an increasing spot size and laser energy resulted in a higher response. The variation was higher for a laser energy below 70%. The variation in the integrated range of the laser signal was also evaluated, but this did not vary a lot. Figure S4 shows the combined results. The combination of a 100% laser with a 100 μm spot gives the highest counts for a relatively good RSD. The application of a 100% laser with an 80 μm spot gives the best RSD with relatively good counts. Settings combining 90% laser and 90 μm spot or 80% laser with 100 μm spot are in between those values. The within RSD is shown, but a similar trend was visible for the between RSD.

Figures S5 and S6 show the same results for the PE standards. The combination of a 100% energy laser with a spot size of either 70 μm , 80 μm , or 100 μm gives the best RSD and counts. The results for the PS standards are shown in Figure S7 and S8. The combination of an 85% energy laser with a spot size of 100 μm resulted in the best counts and RSD. The second-best option is using a laser energy of 100% and spot of 80 μm . Overall, the three best options are applying an 85% laser energy with a 100 μm spot or using 100% laser energy with an 80 μm or 100 μm spot.

Figure S2. LA-ICP-MS analysis of mid concentration PVC sample for various spot sizes and laser energies. A) Mean cps, B) Mean RSD (%).

Figure S3. Combination of spot size and laser energy settings on the mean RSD (%) and cps (reverse axis is shown) of mid concentration PVC samples. Ideally, the data points should be positioned in the lower left corner.

Figure S4. LA-ICP-MS analysis of mid concentration PE sample for various spot sizes and laser energies. A) Mean cps, B) Mean RSD (%).

Figure S5. Combination of spot size and laser energy settings on the mean RSD (%) and cps (reverse axis is shown) of mid concentration PE samples. Ideally, the data points should be positioned in the lower left corner.

Figure S6. LA-ICP-MS analysis of mid concentration PS sample for various spot sizes and laser energies. A) Mean cps, B) Mean RSD (%).

Figure S7. Combination of spot size and laser energy settings on the mean RSD (%) and cps (reverse axis is shown) of mid concentration PS samples. Ideally, the data points should be positioned in the lower left corner.

4.2. Line ablations of mid concentration samples

The three best spot settings were applied to lines as well, but in this case the length and the laser speed were also varied. Figure S9 shows the results for mid concentrations samples of PVC, PE, and PS. Overall, a low speed of 0.015 mm/s with a line length of 0.7 mm was better than a speed of 0.1 mm/s with 3-line ablations over a length of 1.4 mm. Although a spot size of 100 μm with a laser energy of 80% was the best for PVC, this was the worst for PE. The setting of 85% laser energy and 100 μm line width was relatively good for all polymers, followed by a combination of 100% laser energy and a line width of 100 μm .

Figure S8. Combination of spot size and laser energy settings on the mean RSD (%) and cps (reverse axis is shown) of mid concentration samples measured in line mode (0.7 mm, 0.015 mm/s). Ideally, the data points should be positioned in the lower left corner. A) PVC, B) PE, C) PS.

4.3. Spot and lines for various concentration standards

Based on the previous results, a limited number of preferred settings were selected that were applied to all concentration standards. Spots were measured with either 100 µm spot size with 85% laser energy or 80 µm spot size with 100% laser energy. In addition, lines were measured with 100 µm spot size and 85% or 100% laser energy over a line of 0.7 mm sampled at 0.015 mm/s. Two different ways of integration were evaluated: a small range of 40 s to 60 s and a wider range of 30 s to 60 s. Table S18 shows the performance with the RSD within-sample, RSD within-batch, signal RSD, mean of the maximum values of the elemental concentrations, the abundance of the minimum value compared to the blank, and the number of samples that were below a signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio of 3.

Overall, the best performance was found for 0.7 mm (0.015 mm/s) line ablations with 100 µm spot size, 85% laser energy and an integration range of 30 s to 60 s. This was in accordance with previous results based on a small selection of standards. The described method was selected for further analysis of the samples.

Table S17. Average characteristics of low, medium and high concentration standards analyzed with various settings.

Polymer	Type	Spot (µm)	Laser (%)	Range (s)	RSD within-sample (%)	RSD within-batch (%)	Signal RSD (%)	Max signal (mean)	Min signal/blank (%)	N (S/N<3)
PVC	Line	100	85	40-60	8	21	15	2.2E+06	170	25
PVC	Line	100	85	30-60	7	21	20	1.9E+06	165	25
PVC	Line	100	100	30-60	11	22	18	2.7E+06	116	15
PVC	Spot	80	100	40-60	18	23	25	1.9E+07	23	25
PVC	Spot	100	85	40-60	15	30	22	3.8E+06	906	14
PE	Line	100	85	40-60	13	31	21	4.8E+06	137	14
PE	Line	100	85	30-60	14	33	24	4.7E+06	105	13
PE	Spot	80	100	40-60	20	43	47	3.8E+06	444	12
PE	Spot	100	85	40-60	19	34	32	2.5E+06	468	12
PS	Line	100	85	40-60	29	41	23	4.4E+06	274	24
PS	Line	100	85	30-60	26	39	26	3.5E+06	242	24
PS	Spot	80	100	40-60	44	44	35	4.5E+06	141	25
PS	Spot	100	85	40-60	35	48	29	5.8E+06	293	16

5. Performance of the polymer standard

5.1. Homogeneity

Table S19 compares the mean relative standard deviations for within-sample, between-batch, and between-run variation of the PVC, PE, and PS standards. The within-sample variation was measured based on four replicates within one batch of polymer standard. Additionally, three batches of PE, PS, and PVC standards at three concentrations were analyzed and evaluated for between-batch variation and linearity. The between-run variation of the standards was based on measurements repeated on 17 days. Especially, μ -XRF analysis provides a good indication of the homogeneity, since the μ -XRF samples a larger volume. The PS standard shows poor homogeneity which is presumably due to higher background concentrations for multiple elements [5]. For these standards, the μ -XRF results were comparable to the LA-ICP-(TOF-)MS findings.

Table S18. Average relative standard deviation (RSD, 18-160 repetitions) as indicator for within-sample ($n=4$, 68 repetitions), within-batch ($n=3$, 17 repetitions), and between-run variation ($n=14$), for high concentration PE, PS, and PVC standards, analyzed by LA-ICP-MS for 21 elements, and μ -XRF ($n=32$, 3 repetitions) for 12-15 elements. The signals were normalized to the nickel signal and are presented \pm stdv.

	Within sample RSD (%)		Within-batch RSD (%)		Between run (%)
	LA-ICP-MS	μ -XRF	LA-ICP-MS	μ -XRF	LA-ICP-MS
PVC	4.0 ± 1.9	16	10 ± 5	12	17 ± 12
PE	7.2 ± 2.3	10	13 ± 15	12	12 ± 6
PS	16 ± 9	28	23 ± 11	43	21 ± 8

5.2. LA-ICP-MS response

The line ablation signals of four representative elements are shown in Figure S10.

Figure S9. LA-ICP-MS line scans over a distance of 0.7 mm for A) PE, B) PS, and C) PVC standards with four representative elements. Dashed lines mark the start and end of a line scan.

5.3. Signal drift

To evaluate the signal drift, the standards were measured two times a day, i.e., before and after measuring the forensic objects. A mean decrease in elemental signal of 10, 8, and 19% was observed in respectively the PVC, PE, and PS standards. This was reduced by normalization to the signal of one element. Normalizing to carbon gave a maximum drift of -14% and normalization to the nickel signal resulted in a maximum drift of 5%.

5.4. Linearity

To evaluate the linearity, three batches of the blank, low, mid, and high concentration PVC, PE, and PS standards were measured in triplicate. In accordance with previously reported results [5], the LA-ICP-MS analyses showed excellent linear response with R^2 for >0.99 for all elements in the PVC standards (Table S20). For PE, two elements (^{27}Al and ^{44}Ca) showed an R^2 below 0.99, but still above 0.93. For PS ^{47}Ti showed worse performance, probably because of the relatively large within-sample variation of the PS samples. The calibration graphs are shown in Figure S11. The response between the different polymer matrices varied considerably. The level of Pd and Si in PE was six orders of magnitude lower than its concentration in PVC and PS. For the other elements the difference was less apparent, where the highest response was on average seven times higher than the lowest response. To be able to correct for this variation, the PVC and PE polymer standards were both included in the analyses in this study.

Table S19. Linearity of the elemental responses of PVC, PE, and PS reference standards analyzed by LA-ICP-MS.

Element	R^2		
	PVC	PE	PS
Na23	0.9998	0.9999	0.9993
Mg25	0.9999	0.9995	0.9996
Al27	0.9965	0.9354	0.9963
Si29	0.9999	0.9996	0.9975
K39	0.9977	0.9997	1.0000
Ca44	1.0000	0.9886	0.9980
Ti47	1.0000	0.9992	0.5640
Mn55	0.9973	0.9999	1.0000
Fe57	0.9999	0.9999	0.9993
Co59	0.9999	0.9999	0.9994
Ni60	1.0000	0.9998	0.9993
Cu63	1.0000	1.0000	0.9996
Ga69	0.9999	0.9998	0.9991
As75	0.9999	0.9997	0.9990
Sr88	1.0000	0.9999	0.9997
Nb93	0.9961	0.9972	0.9975
Pd106	0.9964	0.9962	0.9995
Sn118	1.0000	0.9999	0.9993
Sb121	0.9934	0.9996	0.9992
Ba138	1.0000	1.0000	0.9998
Pb208	1.0000	0.9994	0.9991

Figure S10. Calibration curves of responses in counts per seconds (CPS) of PE, PS and PVC with an elemental concentration ranging from 0 to 1000 mg/kg analyzed by LA-ICP-MS.

6. Correlation plots

Figure S11. Pearson's correlation coefficients of the elements detected by LA-ICP-MS in tapes, jerrycans, and wires.

7. Leave-one-out validation PCA

Figure S12. Explained variance of PCA with all data or when leaving out one sample.

8. Leave one-out validation LDA

Figure S13. LDA-score plot of predicted values of leave-one-out samples, based on the elemental concentrations of tapes, tubing, and wires measured by LA-ICP-MS. Responses are quantified with the PVC standard and log₁₀ transformed. The figure shows misclassification of eight repetitions of a transparent wire.

Figure S14. LDA values of training set (black dotted line) compared to predicted values based on test set with leave-one-out observation (blue dots). A) First LDA dimension (mean: 23% RSD, median: 2.6% RSD). B) Second LDA dimension (mean: 34% RSD, median: 5.2% RSD).

9. Boxplot of concentrations for each element

Figure S15. Boxplot with median elemental concentrations grouped by the type of forensic object. Elemental concentrations in mg/kg are shown based on correction with the PVC standard.

Figure S16. Boxplot median \log_{10} transformed elemental concentrations of all objects grouped by color. Elemental concentrations are shown based on correction with the PVC standard.

10. False inclusions/exclusions comparison models

Table S20. Rates of misleading evidence for the tape database, calculated by 4 sigma criterion, t-test with Bonferroni correction, MKV feature-based model, and score-based model with SVM and KDE.

Normalization	Elements	False exclusion (%)				False inclusion (%)			
		4s	t-test	Feature	Score	4s	t-test	Feature	Score
Without	18	1.1	4.6	4.6	0	1.2	0.080	1.8	0.65
¹³ C	18	5.7	2.3	2.3	0	0.16	0.094	4.8	0.65
Glass standard	18	40	2.3	4.6	0	0.040	0.027	5.4	0.65
PVC standard	18	2.3	3.4	4.6	0	0.24	0.013	6.0	0.65
¹³ C, PVC standard	18	2.3	1.1	3.4	0	0.24	0	5.1	0.65
Without	9	0	3.4	3.4	11	3.1	0.29	5.4	0.65
¹³ C	9	0	0	3.4	5.6	0.84	0.31	7.7	0.65
Glass standard	9	31	1.1	3.4	0	0.13	0.21	3.6	0.65
PVC standard	9	0	1.1	5.7	5.6	0.86	0.16	4.2	0.65
¹³ C, PVC standard	9	2.3	0	4.6	11	0.95	0.20	2.7	0.65

Table S21 Rates of misleading evidence for the tubing database, calculated by 4 sigma criterion, t-test with Bonferroni correction, MKV feature-based model, and score-based model with SVM and KDE.

Normalization	Elements	False exclusion (%)				False inclusion (%)			
		4s	t-test	Feature	Score	4s	t-test	Feature	Score
Without	18	5.1	0	17	13	11	0.17	14	7.1
¹³ C	18	5.1	5.1	15	0	1.9	0.20	5.3	11
Glass standard*	18	41	2.6	16	0	0.20	0.60	30	7.1
PVC standard	18	2.6	2.6	13	13	8.1	0.34	16	3.6
¹³ C, PVC standard	18	2.6	2.6	18	0	2.3	0.20	5.2	11
Without	9	2.6	0	7.7	0	19	1.2	8.8	11
¹³ C	9	2.6	0	5.1	0	3.7	1.0	11	14
Glass standard*	9	21	2.6	2.6	0	0.40	1.1	14	11
PVC standard	9	0	0	7.7	0	18	1.1	11	18
¹³ C, PVC standard	9	0	0	5.1	0	7.3	1.2	12	11

*Limited repetitions for data corrected for glass standard.

Table S22. Rates of misleading evidence for the wires database, calculated by 4 sigma criterion, t-test with Bonferroni correction, MKV feature-based model, and score-based model with SVM and logistic regression.

Normalization	Elements	False exclusion (%)				False inclusion (%)			
		4s	t-test	Feature	Score	4s	t-test	Feature	Score
Without	18	2.0	0	6.1	10	0.60	0.17	4.2	0
¹³ C	18	16	2.0	2.0	0	0.13	0	2.1	0
Glass standard	18	20	2.0	6.1	0	0.17	0.13	5.2	0
PVC standard	18	6.1	0	4.1	10	2.5	0.085	4.2	0
¹³ C, PVC standard	18	10	2.0	2.0	0	0.26	0	2.1	0
Without	9	0	0	2.0	0	4.2	0.30	0	0
¹³ C	9	14	0	8.2	0	0.89	0.13	1.0	0
Glass standard	9	14	0	4.1	0	0.85	0.38	0	2.2
PVC standard	9	2.0	0	4.1	0	9.2	0.21	0	2.2
¹³ C, PVC standard	9	4.1	0	8.2	0	1.7	0.085	2.1	0

Table S23. Rates of misleading evidence for the jerrycans database, calculated by 4 sigma criterion, t-test with Bonferroni correction, MKV feature-based model, and score-based model with SVM and logistic regression.

Normalization	Elements	False exclusion (%)				False inclusion (%)			
		4s	t-test	Feature	Score	4s	t-test	Feature	Score
Without	18	21	2.6	3.2	0	2.0	1.3	4.4	0
¹³ C	18	13	5.1	0	0	1.4	2.0	2.2	7.1
Glass standard	18	13	2.6	2.9	0	14	0.88	2.0	3.6
PVC standard	18	15	2.6	3.7	0	1.2	0.61	2.6	7.1
¹³ C, PVC standard	18	18	2.6	6.5	13	1.6	2.2	4.4	7.1
Without	9	2.6	0	5.1	0	8.8	4.0	1.8	0
¹³ C	9	5.1	2.6	0	13	6.3	4.1	1.8	3.6
Glass standard	9	10	2.6	2.6	0	27	2.8	1.8	0
PVC standard	9	7.7	0	2.6	0	5.0	2.4	1.8	0
¹³ C, PVC standard	9	7.7	0	2.6	13	5.2	4.0	1.8	3.6

11. Tippett plots feature-based LR model

Figure S17. Tippett plots with PAV-calibrated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the tapes dataset, obtained with the feature-based MVK model. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S18. Tippett plots with PAV-calibrated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the tubing dataset, obtained with the feature-based MVK model. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S19. Tippett plots with PAV-calibrated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the wires dataset, obtained with the feature-based MVK model. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S20. Tippett plots with PAV-calibrated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the jerrycans dataset, obtained with the feature-based MVK model. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

12. Performance measures feature-based LR model

Table S24. Performance measures of the feature-based LR model of the tape dataset after calibration and validation with 18 and 9 elements: log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr), minimum, and maximum log₁₀ PAV LR value.

Elements	Normalization and quantification	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	Without	0.22	-1.81	2.07
	¹³ C	0.19	-1.87	2.06
	Glass standard	0.20	-1.84	2.33
	PVC standard	0.23	-1.84	2.00
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.21	-1.85	2.05
18	Without	0.19	-1.83	2.31
	¹³ C	0.18	-1.89	2.36
	Glass standard	0.17	-1.88	2.33
	PVC standard	0.20	-1.89	2.33
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.17	-1.87	2.34

Table S25. Performance measures of the feature-based LR model of the tubing dataset after calibration and validation with 18 and 9 elements: log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr), minimum, and maximum log₁₀ PAV LR value.

Elements	Normalization and quantification	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	Without	0.43	-1.33	1.28
	¹³ C	0.41	-1.51	1.32
	Glass standard	0.41	-1.51	1.12
	PVC standard	0.39	-1.51	1.25
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.39	-1.48	1.31
18	Without	0.50	-1.41	1.43
	¹³ C	0.40	-1.44	1.57
	Glass standard	0.58	-1.43	1.48
	PVC standard	0.42	-1.46	1.55
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.51	-1.37	1.43

Table S26. Performance measures of the feature-based LR model of the wires dataset after calibration and validation with 18 and 9 elements: log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr), minimum, and maximum log₁₀ PAV LR value.

Elements	Normalization and quantification	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	Without	0.050	-1.65	1.88
	¹³ C	0.21	-1.62	1.87
	Glass standard	0.15	-1.63	1.88
	PVC standard	0.15	-1.61	1.88
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.20	-1.64	1.87
18	Without	0.32	-1.63	1.87
	¹³ C	0.17	-1.63	1.89
	Glass standard	0.27	-1.63	1.87
	PVC standard	0.26	-1.63	1.88
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.12	-1.64	1.89

Table S27. Performance measures of the feature-based LR model of the jerrycans dataset after calibration and validation with 18 and 9 elements: log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr), minimum, and maximum log₁₀ PAV LR value.

Elements	Normalization and quantification	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	Without	0.22	-1.55	1.67
	¹³ C	0.049	-1.56	1.68
	Glass standard	0.14	-1.56	1.68
	PVC standard	0.14	-1.56	1.68
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.14	-1.56	1.68
18	Without	0.21	-1.55	1.65
	¹³ C	0.059	-1.56	1.68
	Glass standard	0.17	-1.56	1.68
	PVC standard	0.15	-1.54	1.67
	¹³ C, PVC standard	0.23	-1.55	1.67

13. Tippett plots score-based LR model

Figure S21. Tippett plots with the validated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the tapes dataset, obtained by the score-based model with SVM scoring system. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S22. Tippett plots with the validated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the tubing dataset, obtained by the score-based model with SVM scoring system. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S23. Tippett plots with the validated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the wires dataset, obtained by the score-based model with SVM scoring system. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

Figure S24. Tippett plots with the validated cumulative distributions of \log_{10} likelihood ratio (LR) values for the jerrycans dataset, obtained by the score-based model with SVM scoring system. A) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C . B) Elemental concentrations normalized to ^{13}C and quantified with the PVC standard.

14. Performance measures score-based LR model

Table S28. Performance measures of the score-based LR model of the tape database with log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr) and minimum and maximum likelihood ratio values with empirical lower and upper bounds (ELUB) before validation.

Elements	Correction	Measure	LR to score	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.29	-1.70	2.00
			Logreg	0.30	-1.69	2.04
		SVM	KDE	0.25	-1.65	2.43
			Logreg	0.26	-1.62	2.52
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.16	-1.70	1.97
			Logreg	0.16	-1.69	1.99
		SVM	KDE	0.44	-1.73	2.40
			Logreg	0.31	-1.69	2.20
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.09	-1.72	2.20
			Logreg	0.10	-1.71	2.42
		SVM	KDE	0.11	-1.67	2.65
			Logreg	0.11	-1.63	2.34
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.30	-1.71	2.09
			Logreg	0.27	-1.70	2.11
		SVM	KDE	0.47	-1.73	2.38
			Logreg	0.30	-1.68	2.29
C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.30	-1.70	2.06	
		Logreg	0.30	-1.69	2.12	
	SVM	KDE	0.48	-1.73	2.45	
		Logreg	0.34	-1.68	2.32	
18	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.18	-1.72	2.28
			Logreg	0.19	-1.71	2.61
		SVM	KDE	0.13	-1.62	3.04
			Logreg	0.11	-1.63	2.85
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.10	-1.72	2.18
			Logreg	0.10	-1.71	2.47
		SVM	KDE	0.08	-1.74	2.95
			Logreg	0.07	-1.73	2.91
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.10	-1.74	2.45
			Logreg	0.11	-1.73	2.52
		SVM	KDE	0.11	-1.74	2.87
			Logreg	0.09	-1.71	2.46
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.12	-1.72	2.31
			Logreg	0.14	-1.72	2.68
		SVM	KDE	0.12	-1.74	3.04
			Logreg	0.10	-1.72	3.03
	C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.13	-1.72	2.32
			Logreg	0.18	-1.71	2.65
		SVM	KDE	0.09	-1.74	3.04
			Logreg	0.09	-1.71	3.01

Table S29. Performance measures of the score-based LR model of the tubing database with log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr) and minimum and maximum likelihood ratio values with empirical lower and upper bounds (ELUB) before validation.

Elements	Correction	Measure	LR to score	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.26	-1.16	1.29
			Logreg	0.28	-0.93	1.36
		SVM	KDE	0.15	-1.06	1.52
			Logreg	0.16	-0.95	1.44
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.28	-1.15	1.21
			Logreg	0.28	-0.93	1.34
		SVM	KDE	0.25	-1.16	1.65
			Logreg	0.22	-0.94	1.52
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.31	-1.22	1.31
			Logreg	0.26	-1.24	1.51
		SVM	KDE	0.26	-1.17	1.56
			Logreg	0.24	-0.85	1.64
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.24	-1.19	1.33
			Logreg	0.24	-1.21	1.42
		SVM	KDE	0.14	-1.06	1.51
			Logreg	0.16	-0.93	1.41
C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.28	-1.19	1.23	
		Logreg	0.29	-0.93	1.25	
	SVM	KDE	0.25	-1.19	1.50	
		Logreg	0.19	-1.21	1.52	
18	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.17	-1.31	1.52
			Logreg	0.15	-1.29	1.48
		SVM	KDE	0.06	-1.36	2.08
			Logreg	0.06	-1.26	2.09
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.23	-1.30	1.44
			Logreg	0.22	-1.29	1.42
		SVM	KDE	0.13	-1.36	1.85
			Logreg	0.13	-1.28	1.95
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.19	-1.26	1.44
			Logreg	0.17	-1.26	1.74
		SVM	KDE	0.18	-1.00	1.78
			Logreg	0.14	-0.95	1.78
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.17	-1.32	1.52
			Logreg	0.15	-1.31	1.44
		SVM	KDE	0.06	-1.37	2.01
			Logreg	0.07	-1.27	1.71
	C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.21	-1.29	1.46
			Logreg	0.21	-1.29	1.69
		SVM	KDE	0.18	-1.36	1.99
			Logreg	0.14	-1.29	1.85

Table S30. Performance measures of the score-based LR model of the wires database with log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr) and minimum and maximum likelihood ratio values with empirical lower and upper bounds (ELUB) before validation.

Elements	Correction	Measure	LR to score	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.34	-1.49	2.12
			Logreg	0.22	-1.48	2.34
		SVM	KDE	0.47	-1.50	2.54
			Logreg	0.35	-1.49	2.39
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.43	-1.49	2.16
			Logreg	0.23	-1.48	2.37
		SVM	KDE	0.49	-1.50	2.52
			Logreg	0.33	-1.49	2.48
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.32	-1.49	2.16
			Logreg	0.22	-1.48	2.34
		SVM	KDE	0.47	-1.50	2.52
			Logreg	0.33	-1.49	2.39
PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.42	-1.49	2.20	
		Logreg	0.21	-1.49	2.34	
	SVM	KDE	0.45	-1.50	2.54	
		Logreg	0.31	-1.49	2.39	
C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.43	-1.49	2.18	
		Logreg	0.22	-1.48	2.37	
	SVM	KDE	0.49	-1.50	2.52	
		Logreg	0.34	-1.49	2.48	
18	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.09	-1.49	2.28
			Logreg	0.06	-1.48	2.41
		SVM	KDE	0.34	-1.50	2.59
			Logreg	0.13	-1.49	2.41
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.35	-1.49	2.31
			Logreg	0.14	-1.49	2.48
		SVM	KDE	0.34	-1.50	2.56
			Logreg	0.14	-1.49	2.39
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.05	-1.49	2.28
			Logreg	0.07	-1.49	2.41
		SVM	KDE	0.34	-1.50	2.59
			Logreg	0.13	-1.49	2.39
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.05	-1.49	2.28
			Logreg	0.06	-1.49	2.41
		SVM	KDE	0.34	-1.50	2.62
			Logreg	0.10	-1.49	2.34
	C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.26	-1.49	2.30
			Logreg	0.12	-1.49	2.48
		SVM	KDE	0.34	-1.50	2.58
			Logreg	0.13	-1.49	2.39

Table S31. Performance measures of the score-based LR model of the jerrycans database with log-likelihood-ratio cost (Cllr) and minimum and maximum likelihood ratio values with empirical lower and upper bounds (ELUB) before validation.

Elements	Correction	Measure	LR to score	Cllr	Min log ₁₀ LR	Max log ₁₀ LR
9	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.77	-1.34	1.88
			Logreg	0.79	-1.33	2.24
		SVM	KDE	0.71	-1.38	2.32
			Logreg	0.74	-1.38	2.27
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.38	-1.19	1.85
			Logreg	0.38	-0.99	1.95
		SVM	KDE	0.37	-1.29	2.30
			Logreg	0.37	-1.28	2.17
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.43	-1.37	1.88
			Logreg	0.45	-1.35	2.22
		SVM	KDE	0.40	-1.39	2.30
			Logreg	0.44	-1.38	2.27
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.59	-1.32	2.22
			Logreg	0.59	-1.32	2.22
		SVM	KDE	0.70	-1.38	2.32
			Logreg	0.71	-1.38	2.27
C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.50	-1.19	1.85	
		Logreg	0.43	-0.99	1.95	
	SVM	KDE	0.54	-1.29	2.30	
		Logreg	0.52	-1.05	2.16	
18	No correction	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.78	-1.38	2.16
			Logreg	0.82	-1.38	2.32
		SVM	KDE	0.83	-1.39	2.34
			Logreg	0.80	-1.39	2.30
	C	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.38	-1.30	2.30
			Logreg	0.37	-1.32	2.25
		SVM	KDE	0.41	-1.39	2.41
			Logreg	0.40	-1.35	2.34
	glass	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.40	-1.39	2.20
			Logreg	0.40	-1.38	2.32
		SVM	KDE	0.37	-1.39	2.38
			Logreg	0.41	-1.39	2.27
	PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.51	-1.38	2.25
			Logreg	0.53	-1.38	2.32
		SVM	KDE	0.45	-1.39	2.38
			Logreg	0.49	-1.38	2.30
	C, PVC	Manhattan distance	KDE	0.41	-1.30	2.30
			Logreg	0.39	-1.32	2.25
		SVM	KDE	0.40	-1.37	2.40
			Logreg	0.42	-1.34	2.32

Disclaimer

Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this paper in order to specify the experimental procedure adequately. Such identification is not intended to imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Institute of Standards and Technology, nor is it intended to imply that the materials or equipment identified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

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